
A Critical Appraisal of Social Media and Advertising and its Roles in Promoting Product and Services

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Abstract

New media advertising focuses on promoting brands and selling products or services through established and emerging online channels, through engagements of current and potential customers. New media advertising and marketing encompasses many different mediums, including display advertisements, content marketing and social media promotions. The objective of all new media advertising and marketing is to get consumers to interact with the brand, engaging them in a way that increases awareness and correlates with sales. This paper assess the new media and advertising; it explicates how new media affect advertising. The paper's design method is a narrative literature review and the data sources included Google scholar, blogs and the web of science. Books, print journals, magazines, were also used. The paper outlined and discussed issues raised into themes concerning new media or social media and advertising. The study concludes that social media play an important role in promoting product, services and ideas.

Keywords: New Media, Social Media, Advertising, Marketing

Word Count: 150

Introduction

New media are becoming popular nowadays It is significant to understand the role social media sites play and continue to play in globalisation. Boyutta (2012), points out that; Globalization via the use of social media sites has huge impact on our daily activities. Since the beginning of the World Wide Web (WWW), nations have become more connected with each other. The twenty-first century is developing into a time of technological changes. There is steady change and addition to the available technological resources. As it advances, it also spreads globally. The worldwide spread of technology creates vast connections that create new opportunities on a larger degree. The current focus of the

globalization of technology is the connections created by networks of social media or new media. New media is a brilliant tool that can be easily used by those who have access to it. The access of new media is gained globally; there is no any part of the world neglected, it creates opportunities to those who are first experiencing the use to outsource ideas. Currently, the use of social media is being used to implement changes. Connecting to the social media sites or network helps people all over the globe to connect for different purposes. For instance, we can connect with other people, organisations, ideas and information that were not available to us before the invention of social media. This is the new way of understanding other people's character and behaviour, and it also helps in getting first-hand information without being distorted by mainstream media.

Mizuko (2008) points out that online space enable youth to connect with peers in new ways. Most youth use online networks to extend the friendships that they navigate in the familiar contexts of schools, religious organizations, sports, and other local activities. They can be 'always on,' in constant contact with their friends via texting, instant messaging, mobile phones, and Internet connections. The significant number of youth uses 'social media' to explore interests and look for other information that goes beyond what they can access in school or in their society. In these modern days such network closeness is important because it bears on the ability of agents to form new links.

To sum it up, new media provide additional advantages better than what internet provide. People are interactively connected with one another, social media interaction allows for the accelerated flow of information for grass-roots struggles, as well as a free medium of communication to date. Social Media sites are the place where millions of people interact and exchange ideas. Therefore, advertisers see Social Media as an avenue where they can meet their target or potential customers. The aim of advertising is to increase commercial profits and the demand of the consumers. This study tries to explores nexus between social media networks and advertising; how new media or social media affect advertising. To better understand the hub of this study, figure 1 below captures the themes to be covered in this study.

Fig. 1: Study Structure and Themes that Form the Literature

Social Media Network

The importance humans attach to communication has led to search for avenues to communicate with people all around the world at the same time during any given time. Hence the invention of different technologies enhances communication both at the interpersonal and mass communication levels. The latest and recent of these inventions is the ‘Social Media’.

Social Media sites are the place where millions of people interact and exchange ideas. Therefore, advertisers see Social Media as an avenue where they can meet their target or potential customers. Before the use of internet and social network sites became popular, communication over long distances were very minimal. With the invention of the World Wide Web the internet became a global network and use of social network sites played a vital role in shaping the world to become information age or new media age.

Social Media is also a driving force of information, because it gives an individual the ability to create and consume information immediately and distributes it on the internet, at the same time Social Media gives users an opportunity to obtain and share instant information and content with friends. Thus, advertisers and companies cannot afford to ignore the importance of Social Media. In fact, if a company wants to survive today it must compute in the aspect of Social Media.

According to Edwards (2011), Social Media consists networks such as; Facebook, MySpace, and LinkedIn. NYC (2012), Department of education has similar view, the department define Social Media as: “any form of online publication or presence that allows interactive communication, including, but not limited to, social networks, blogs, internet websites, internet forums, and wikis. Examples of Social Media include; Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Google+, and Flickr.”(p. 92). This revealed that, Social Media is a broad environment that comprises video sharing sites, photo sharing sites, search engines and information searching site like Wikipedia. According to Ryan and Jones (2009);

Social Media is the umbrella term for web-based software and services that allow users to come together online and exchange, discuss, communicate and participate in any form of social interaction that interaction can encompass text, audio, text, audio, images, video and other media, individually or in any combination (p. 152).

People discuss the hot topic of the day via Social Media. Users also share and recommend products, services and brand as well as rating and reviewing. Not only that users share their experience and proficiency. Thus, target audience are now the active participants of debate. It's further noted that Social Media is about networking and connecting by engaging in conversations through technology. People share thoughts, activities and engage in conversations of interest to them. They do this by connecting with people of similar interests or backgrounds such as; hobbies or professional interests, high school classmates, family and friends, co-workers among others. (Packer, 2011). Different categories of people engage in Social Media and discuss issues related to their interest, and some time creates community. Speedy expansion in the use of Social Media across the globe shows that companies can use it to develop their product and service to tally consumer's interest (Mir, 2012).

Social media network is almost everywhere in the world, if a company carries their customers along, the customers will talk about the product, when the customer's interests are neglected then the advertising will not go viral. Social Media has advanced from simply providing a platform for individuals to stay in touch with their family and friends now it is a place where consumers can learn more about their desired companies and the products. Marketers and retailers are utilizing these sites as another way to reach consumers and provide a new way to shop (Paquette, 2013). The use of Social Media nowadays is incredible, Hensel and Deis

(2010) indicates that the massive volume of data provided by Social Media will provide challenges and opportunities.

With the invention of Social Media the use of traditional media is dramatically decreased. “The rapid increase in online media usage led to a decrease in the popularity of other media sources during the three-year period. Struggling media sources include TV, radio, newspaper, and magazine” (social media today, 2013). Meanwhile, Social Media provide avenues and opportunities that tally with the interest of twenty-one century, emerging life without Social Media; some of the benefit or the aim of globalization will not be achieve. Many industries use Social Media to burst their marketing, and also help to meet the demand of their customers. Social Media technologies are disrupting the broadcast ‘one-to-many’ media model, consumers has opportunity to give feedback (Barefoot and Szabo, 2010). This means that Social Media is a two-way communication in which sometime customers participate in company decision process.

Social Media is the prospect of communication, a multiple array of internet based apparatus and platforms that improve the sharing of ideas or information. This innovation of media increase transfer of information among internet users; the enormous group of internet tools increases every day and social avenues to reach various and widespread population is also increase. (Cruz, 2012). As a result of this widespread it’s important if not necessary for the company to engage in Social Media activity; not just engage but to make proper use of it in order to compete with other competitors around.

Classification of Social Media Network

There are different forms of Social Media, scholars has different views in categorizing Social Media, and some Social Media sites are out-up-date while new ones are yet to come. Every day we may come across with the new ones. Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) believes that; “there is no systematic way in which different Social Media applications can be categorized” (p. 61). Ryan and Jones (n.d) classified Social Media into ten categories namely: social bookmarking, Social Media submission sites, forums and discussion sites, media sharing sites, review and rating sites, social network sites, blogs, podcasts, micro-blogging and wikis. Grahl (2014)

narrow down Social Media network into six, to his view all categories of Social Media fall into these six categories.

- **Social Networks:** These give users the opportunity to connect with people of similar interest and background. Social network sites usually contain profiles, allow users to create groups and share information with other user. Typical examples of Social Network sites include; *Facebook* and *LinkedIn*. Multiple numbers of people use social network sites and the numbers are increasing every day. Social Network sites provide flexible advertising option for business and allow organisations to set up their own pages or profiles.
- **Bookmarking Sites:** Social bookmarking sites allow users to save ‘bookmark’ favourite web pages and organize the pages by using tag. This allows users to access the sites easily and share with friends. The most common examples of bookmarking sites are *delicious.com*, *ma.gnolia.com*, and *stumbleupon.com*.
- **Social News:** Social News sites also called ‘Social Media sites’; the sites allow users to post different News items or links and users can vote on the items, the more vote for a particular item, the higher up the rankings it rises. And the items with higher votes are displayed at home page. The most popular example of Social News sites are: *digg.com*, *reddit.com* and *sphinn.com*. Social News sites help organisations or marketers to find out what people are interested in.
- **Media Sharing:** These are popular nowadays, the site allow users to upload; share, and comment on photos and videos. Examples of media sharing sites are: *YouTube*, *Flickr*, Instagram and *Picasa*.
- **Micro-blogging:** Micro-blogging site is the site that gives users an opportunity to share short messages to their friends in order to keep them up-to-date, the text is usually not less than 160 characters. The most popular example of micro-blogging is *Twitter.com*, Twitter allow users to send short text of 140 characters.
- **Blog Comments and Forums:** Blog is one of the earliest forms of Social Media; people use blogs to report local news, express opinions, vision and experiences. Forums allow users to hold conversations by posting messages. A popular example of such Forums is the *Yahoo groups*. Forums give a company an insight into what consumers are talking about, what makes them tick.

It very difficult if not impossible for the company to engage in all forms of Social Media sites. The most important for the company is to know where their target audience are; which Social Media are they using. Some industries believed that if you are not participating in Social Media; you are not part of cyberspace any more (Kaplan, 2010).

Social Media Advertising

In today's sophisticated world, Social Media sites have become an avenue where companies can extend their marketing campaigns to a wider range of consumers. Social Media Marketing is the most recent marketing concept and every business owner wants to know how Social Media can generate value for their companies. Social Media Marketing is about understanding how new technology is making it easier for people to connect socially with their social networks and how business can make profit from that perception (Packer, 2011). Social Media advertising or Social Media marketing is an innovation which forces companies, business tycoons, advertisers to change their marketing strategies from traditional way to modern way or from main stream to new media, because people shun from patronising traditional media. When company advertising their product Social Media, they are doing two things; that is advertising the product and company. For example, many company holders produce different product, when advertising a single product of the company people are likely to know more about the company and its other products.

Social Media advertising is considered to be one of the viral advertising or word-of-mouth marketing. For instance, online users use to communicate with their offline friends about the product or services they come across in Social Media, and share the page or product to online users; as a result of this the advertising will go viral. Social Media advertising is a powerful communication force and significant marketing tool to sell product, services and ideas. Companies use Social Media to advertise their products and services, and reach large number of audience at relatively cheap price (Mon, 2013).

Chen (n.d) observes some key reasons for using Social Media to advertise products, brands or services. These are:

- i. Personalise Interaction: engagement by interacting with customers directly and enhancing customer feedback.

- ii. Boost brand awareness: by using Social Media, companies create awareness, and create present of the same platform that customers use in their daily activities.
- iii. Protect reputation: by using Social Media, company can quickly respond to any rumour or negative publicity concerning the company and give the clear version about the issue.
- iv. Inexpensive: using Social Media is relatively cheaper, it help the company to save time and money.
- v. Problem solving: users can use their knowledge to provide new idea to the company or help in solving company's problem.

A successful Social Media advertising campaign is designed to create quick move. Social Media advertising is an entity that works along a variety that is ever image. The successes of campaign advertisements depend entirely on the marketer's ability to persuade social network users to discuss and promote a product (Naidoo, 2011). When advertising message is very effective users will talk more and more about it, and this will make the advertising message to become viral. Whatever type of business you have i.e. small, medium or big business you can reach your target customers or potential customers via Social Media, because Social Media consist different calibre of people. Whether you are part of a small, medium, or enormous business, or are an individual entrepreneur, your target audiences are using Social Media, and there's no reason you shouldn't be, too. It costs almost nothing, it's easy to get started, and it can have an enormous financial impact on your business (Zarella, 2010).

Social Media advertising is relatively cheaper, it's very important for small and medium entrepreneur to use Social Media to create awareness and boost their business, because customers use Social Media to seek information about the product or service. You don't need to have a big company before joining social media platforms, medium and small company also count.

Types of Social Media Advertising

As a result of Social Media companies are spending billions of dollars/naira to advertise online or specifically on Social Media. Online advertising is very effective and useful to companies. It is no longer an exaggeration when we said it is hard for business to survive in 21st century without been on social media. Take for instance; if the product is targeted to young adult, the best way to reach them is through social media. Young adults are not

patronizing mainstream media. Online advert allow companies to advertise their brand, product and services in a way that catches attention of customers.

Banner Ads

Is a form of advertising done on the web, it's a small Ad on the web page; when the users click on it, it takes a user from one site to another. Banner Ads appear on top, bottom or sides of the web page. This type of Ad is also called 'Click Through'. Banner Ads usually appear horizontally on the web page.

Fig. 2: Banner Ads
Source: Goggle Images

Skyscrapers

Skyscraper Ads are tall and do appear on the web page usually placed on right or left side of a web site. When users click on a skyscraper Ad, they are redirected to the advertiser's website. Skyscrapers are an opposite of a banner advert it appears vertically on the web page on either the left or right sides.

Fig. 3: Skyscraper Ads
Source: Goggle Images

Pop-ups and pop-behind

This is an Ad burst open on the computer screen either in front or behind the opening page of the web site.

Fig. 4: Pop-ups and Pop-behind Ads
Source: Goggle Images

Mini-sites

Mini sites Ad allow marketers to advertise their brand without re-directing users to other sites.

Fig. 5: Mini-site Ads
Source: Goggle Images

Advertisers use such online advertising to make users visit their page. Online Ad allows advertisers to reach significantly more people than traditional media at a low cost.

Importance of Social Media Advertising

Ryan and Jones (2009) discuss some potential benefits of engaging customers through Social Media:

- i. **Stay informed:** The most important of advertising on Social Media is to stay informed. A company can easily understand what its customers think about in relation to the brand; product or services. What customers are saying about the entire company, this well help the company to create effective marketing campaign base on customer's interest.
- ii. **Raise your Company Profile:** The Company can protect their reputation and lift their profile by engaging proactively via Social Media.
- iii. **Level the Playing Field:** By using Social Media, the company gives everyone the same advantages or opportunities, and receive customer's feedback with little or zero amount.
- iv. **Influence the influencers:** The people who are most active users in Social Media circles will be the element of your target market who can be classified as 'influencers', while small in number compared to the market as a whole, influential individuals have already gained respect and trust from their online friends and mentioning their opinion about the product can bring greater impact to the company's status or reputation.

- v. **Nurture Brand Advocacy:** By engaging wisely and positively with people who already have an optimistic attitude towards brand, such people can lift the company knowingly or unknowingly by advocating through Social Media.
- vi. **Pass it on:** Another powerful aspect of Social Media is its power for viral circulation. This is similar to word-of-mouth, apart from that; the word online can travel further and faster. A high-profile news story about company or a post on blog that's picked up and distributed by the readers, if it hits the right note, suddenly it's everywhere. If you get it right, there's no more effective way to promote your business than this.
- vii. **The Wisdom of the Crowd:** When using Social Media, the company getting input from online communities, this input can help in the company output. Example, online communities can help the company to solve business dilemmas and provide answers to some of the company most challenging problems. By going through customers feedback company can make proper research, design and develop decision based on what customers want. It is said that; 'two heads are better than one' this means that; two people may be able to solve a problem that an individual cannot.

Conclusion

It's obvious that any company that want grow nowadays must not ignore Social Media. Bendror (2014), indicates perfect benefits of Social Media ads, these include: improve sales, increase traffic, increase exposure, Developed loyal fans, Improved search ranking, grew business partnerships, reduced marketing expenses and provided marketplace insight. Social Media is playing vital role in how customer participate and share information online. The use of Social Media is far beyond broadcasting brand, product or services; it also creates a good rapport between the company and customers. Without doubt companies that use Social Media to advertise their products are getting quick attention compared to those offline.

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Globalization, Information and Communication and Media Practices; Are Developing Countries Fairing Well?

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Abstract

Globalization occurs from the removal of operational and communication barriers between local, national and international economies to encourage easy communication and improved socio-economic activities. Nevertheless, in relation to developing countries, globalization has brought about commendable changes as well as alterations to certain socio-cultural and economic practices of the underdeveloped countries. This paper looks at these dimensions vis-à-vis the implications. It behooves individual nations particularly developing and under developed to formulate enduring policies that will promote mutual benefits in all facets of life.

Key Words: Globalization, Information Technology, and Communication Media, Developing Countries.

Word Count: 82

Introduction

Globalization is a contemporary and controversial concept that has attracted divergent viewpoints, opinions and propositions about what it is, what its not and the likes. In fact current public discourse about globalization hooves around whether it even exists, when it started, whether it has replaced communism and whether it is more important than regionalism and localism (Stallings 2000). Some even argue that globalization is hypocritical as

developed countries are exploiting developing ones under the guise of helping them. Proponents of globalization say it brings new opportunities to everyone, while anti-globalization groups suggest it harms the majority of the world's population. Globalization is an irreversible reality of contemporary human life. It is a complex and sometimes a paradoxical process, it tries to integrate the world into a global village, at the same time, it breaks down traditional institutions. It has brought about unequal consequences that even the efficiency gains are being challenged by sectors that are hurt by the conduct of liberalization and deregulation of the economy (Tereso, 2002).

More often than not, globalization is seen from the economic perspective by many. However, interactivity across race, borders, continents and the universe at large touching various human endeavor points to the fact that there is more to globalization than from the narrow economic view. Globalization; the oneness of place and time; is not, however, solely or essentially material or techno-economic; it also has cultural social and political bearings. Nevertheless, globalization cannot totally be discussed without the intertwines of trade and commerce around the globe. No doubts, globalization opens up opportunities for development. As such, any discussion on globalization is incomplete without an understanding of the various aspects of the phenomenon: the driving forces that have brought it about; its essential characteristics which will reflect in its impacts; the various areas of human activity where its manifestation can be seen in most tangible forms (e.g. economic, technological, cultural, political and educational). Therefore, this essay will discuss what globalization entails, its economic, cultural, political, environmental, social and technological touch points as well as the good, bad and the ugly sides of globalization within the context of communication and media practices of developing countries.

The Concept of Globalization

Opinion differs on what constitutes globalization. Regardless, there is a common thematic viewpoint that globalization is the process through which organizations, countries, individuals, businesses develop international affiliations and influences by operating on an international scale using communication and technology. Globalization refers to the increasing complexity and interdependence of the world as a whole and to the processes and mechanisms involved (Ritzer, 2011). Globalization involves economic integration; the transfer of policies across borders; the transmission of knowledge; cultural stability; the reproduction, relations, and discourses of power; it is a global process, a concept, a revolution, and an establishment of the global market free from sociopolitical control. It has helped to liberalize national economics by creating a global market place in

which all nations must participate directly or indirectly: This undoubtedly led to growing activities and power of international financial investors mainly presented by multi-national corporations (Jaja,2010 cited in Adesina 2012: 193).

Historically, the roots of globalization run deep, therefore, ascertaining the actual time globalization started is not an easy task particularly as opinions vary. Some scholars argue that there have been various fluctuations of globalization. While many other scholars focused only on the newer periods of globalization, dating the history of globalization to more recent time times (whether it was the telephone, automobiles, air travel, or the Internet), globalization is as old as the human race. Yet the dramatic changes in terms of space and time being brought about by the communications and information revolution represent a qualitative break with the past(Eclac 2002). As a matter of fact, while there is significant attention to recent globalization patterns and trends, scholars argue that the history of globalization can be found as early as the first humans, and even earlier. Some researchers like Michael Bordo (2002), Ritzer (2011: 23) posit that the origins of the history of globalization can be traced back to the ancient civilizations, they maintain that:

The example of the earliest forms of globalization is the trade links between the Sumerian civilization and the Indus Valley Civilization. In fact, after this age, there were numerous instances where trade links were established between various countries like India, Egypt, Greece, and Roman Empire and so on. There were regular business links between the Parthian Empire, Roman Empire and Han Dynasty.

Michael Bordo (2002), Ritzer (2011: 23) also argued that “Globalization, in the sense of increased integration of international markets, has waxed and waned throughout history. Most recently, it thrived between the middle of the nineteenth century and World War I, languished and retreated until about 1970, and has thrived again since then. In addition, Everett, 2015 claimed that the end of the Cold War, the proliferation of the internet, and neo-liberal trade policies all contributed to a greater sense of global interconnectedness in the 1990s. Academics, politicians, and pundits explained these changes in terms of a global identity and a global process of modernization. Therefore the origin and history of globalization can be analyzed through five perspectives with each perspective discarding earlier submissions on the history of globalization (Ritzer, 2011).

Firstly, globalization can be seen as being hardwired into humans, in the form of a basic urge for a better life. This instinct results in the spread of globalization through commerce,

religion, politics, and warfare (Nayan Chanda 2007 : xiv) which focuses on four specific aspects of globalization that relate to a basic “urge” for a better life – trade (or commerce), missionary work (religion), adventures and conquest (politics and warfare). So, as more and more people started traveling to various countries across the world, it led to more communication between people and intermingling of languages and culture.

Secondly, perspective sees globalization as a long - term cyclical process. In this view, there have been other global ages prior to the present one, and each age is destined to contract and disappear, after attaining a peak. In fact, this perspective argues that there have long been cycles of globalization and it is those cycles that are of utmost importance, not any particular phase or point of origin (Scholte 2005 cited by Ritzler 2011). This view, seems to contradict the idea that we live today in a new “global age.” Rather, it suggests that there have been other global ages in the past and that what now appears to be a new global age, or the high point of such an age, is destined to contract and disappear in the future. Eventually, it will also, be replaced by a new cycle in the globalization process.

Thirdly, globalization can be viewed as a series of historical epochs or waves, each with its own point of origin. Therborn,(2000 : 151 cited by Ritzler , 2011) pinpoints six great epochs, or “waves,” of globalization, that have occurred sequentially, each with its own point of origin namely: (i)The fourth to the seventh centuries which witnessed the globalization of religions (e.g. Christianity, Islam) : infact, the Islamic period in the medieval era is an important epoch in the history of globalization. This was when the Jewish and the Muslim traders started going to various parts of the world to sell various items., (ii) The late fifteenth century highlighted by European colonial conquests. (iii)The late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries during which various intra -European wars led to globalization. (iv)The mid - nineteenth century to 1918; the heyday of European imperialism. (v) The post - World War II period. (vi) The post - Cold War period. From this, Therborn, (2000) concludes that globalization today is not unique. However, his historical or epochal view also rejects the cyclical view of globalization. Past epochs are not returning, at least in their earlier form, at some point in the future.

A fourth view is that instead of cycles or great epochs, one can point to much more specific events that can be seen as the origin of globalization and give one a good sense of its history. It argues that the multiple points of origin of globalization are located in seminal historical events and that instead of cycles or great epochs, one can point to much more specific events that can be seen as the origin of globalization which gives a good narration of its history. In fact, according to Ritzler (2011:18), there are many such possible points of origin of globalization, some of which are: the Romans and their far - ranging conquests in the centuries before Christ (Gibbon 1998): the rise and spread of Christianity in the centuries after the fall of the Roman Empire: the spread

of Islam in the seventh century and beyond : European colonialism, especially in the nineteenth century: the travels of the Vikings from Europe to Iceland, Greenland, and briefly y to North America in the ninth through the eleventh centuries : The industrial revolution in the 19th century was one of the major periods in the history of globalization. Due to the industrial revolution, there was a significant increase in the quantity and quality of the products. This led to higher exports and better trade and business relations. The phase of pre globalization perhaps came to an end after the First World War: the launch of the satellite Telstar and soon thereafter the fi rst transatlantic television broadcasts :the transmission from a satellite of the picture of the earth as a single location, not only leading to a greater sense of the world as one place; increased global consciousness [Robertson and Inglis,2004 : 38 – 49 cited in Ritzler 2011) but also of great importance to the development of the global environmental movement: the creation of the Clearing House Interbank Payment System (CHIPS) and global transfers of funds in the 70s: the founding of the modern Internet based on Arpanet in 1988 (which was created in 1969; though it took the Internet several years to take off, this was a turning point in global interconnection for billions of people: the terrorist attacks on September 11, 2001 on the Twin Towers in New York and on the Pentagon in Washington. All these, of course, brought the world very close to the present day and it is possible that other specific events (especially the Great Recession which began in late 2007) will almost certainly come to be associated by future observers with the birth, or further development of globalization.

A fifth view focuses on broader, more recent changes in the twentieth century. There is a sense in this view that a sea change occurred in the last half of the twentieth century. Three of these momentous changes have been identified by scholars as the point of origin of globalization as it exists today: (i) the emergence of the United States as the global power in the years following World War II. Globalization, in the modern sense of the term, came into existence after the Second World War. One of the main factors for this was the plan by the world leaders to break down the borders for fostering trade relations between nations. It was also in this period that major countries like India, Sri Lanka, Indonesia and some countries in South America gained independence. As a result, these countries started having their own economic systems and established trade relations with the rest of the world. (ii) the emergence of the multinational corporations and (iii) the demise of the Soviet Union and the end of the Cold War. It could be argued that globalization is even more recent and did not truly begin until the fall of the “ Iron Curtain ” and the Soviet Union in 1991. With those events, the division of the world into mainly “ capitalist ” and “ communist ” spheres rapidly eroded as did all sorts of barriers that existed between them. Major parts of the world were opened for the first time since the early twentieth century to all sorts of global fl ows; immigration, tourism, media, diplomacy, and especially the capitalistic economic transactions of Multi-national Corporations and other businesses. The global processes that had spread throughout most of the “ free ” world

before 1991 flooded into the now independent states of the old Soviet Union, especially Russia, and most of its allies. China, of course, is becoming a, if not soon the , major force in global capitalism even though the government remains communist, at least in name (Fishman 2006 in Ritzler). In any case, China is actively involved in globalization not only economically, but in many other realms as well (the 2008 Olympics in Beijing is a good example). In addition, the most recent wave of globalization, which started in 1980, was spurred by a combination of advances in transport and communications technologies and by large developing countries who sought foreign investment by opening up to international trade. During this period, wide spread development took place in the field of infrastructure and connectivity. This led to more interaction between the nations and sharing of ideas, culture and tradition. Thus, the perspective adopted here is that globalization is a relatively recent development with its major points of origin occurring before and shortly after the close of World War II.

Globalization and its Theoretical Framework

There are a number of theoretical underpinnings on globalization. Many leading theorists have analyzed globalization in contradictory ways. For instance, some say it is generalised modernity, some say it is post-modernity while some say it is something else entirely. However, a handful as explained by Ritzer will be discussed namely: – imperialism, colonialism (and post - colonialism), development (and dependency), and Americanization. Imperialism describes methods employed by one country to gain territorial control over another, in order to exercise political, economic, and territorial control over it. The idea of imperialism has come to be associated with rule over vast regions. This characteristic leads it to be associated with globalization. The term comes from the Roman imperium (Markoff 2007 : 609 – 14 in Ritzer, 2010:29) and was first associated with domination and political control over one or more neighboring nations. Vladimir Lenin (1917/1939), the first leader of the Soviet Union, was an important early theorist of imperialism, especially in his book, *Imperialism: The Highest Stage of Capitalism* (see also J. A. Hobson 's [1902/1905/1938] *Imperialism*). Lenin argued that economic factors are the essence of imperialism. According to this view, factors inherent in capitalism lead nations to undertake imperial ventures. With such an economic system and imperial ventures, countries to seek out and control distant geographic areas in order to have control over foreign markets and foreign investments needed to provide resources for capitalist industries and also to create new markets for those

industries. In other words, a capitalist economic system tended to expand imperialistically throughout the world through globalization.

On the other hand, Colonialism is clearly related to imperialism (Williams & Chrisman 1994), and the terms are sometimes used interchangeably, but colonialism has a more specific meaning. At the most extreme, imperialism involves a control without the creation of colonies (Harvey 2006: 21 in Ritzer,2011). Colonialism generally involves settlers as well as much more formal mechanisms of political control than those of imperialism. Thus, colonialism often entails the creation by the colonial power in the country (or geographic area) that has been colonized of an administrative apparatus to run its internal affairs, including its settlements such as the case of Nigeria, China, Ghana and some other African countries in the 15th-16th centuries. Colonialism involves more formal mechanisms of control over a territory, entailing the creation of an administrative apparatus to run a colony's internal affairs. The end of WW II saw a strong drive toward decolonization. Colonization was replaced by a more insidious attempt at economic control and exploitation, through neo- colonialism. Post-colonialism relates to developments in former colonies after the departure of the colonizing masters and power. Clearly, it implies the activities carried out after the exit of the colonial powers in once - colonized areas.

Furthermore, Development theory can be seen as a historical stage (roughly the 1940s to the 1970s) that preceded the global age (McMichael 2008: 21 in Ritzer 2011:32). To him, development can be viewed specifically as a “project” that predated the project of globalization. As a project, it was primarily concerned with the economic development of specific nations, usually those that were not regarded as sufficiently advanced economically. Development theory focused on the economic development of specific nations. The project advocated import - substitution, wherein instead of relying on imports from the North, the South was encouraged to produce its own industrial products.

However, a major critique of the development theory project emerged in the form of dependency theory. Adherents of this theory like Andre Gunder Frank (1969) in Ritzer (2011) argued that instead of promoting development, in reality the development theory led to the South ' s greater dependency on the North. Stressing that underdevelopment is not traceable

to internal sources in a particular nation; rather, it is a product of the relationship between developed and underdeveloped countries in the capitalist system.

Americanization is another concept that, like those discussed above, is related to globalization. Ritzer citing Richard Kuisel (1993: 96) defines Americanization as “the import by non - Americans of products, images, technologies, practices and behaviour that are closely associated with America/Americans. ” Long before globalization became a central academic and lay concern, there were many works over a long period of time that dealt with America ’ s global influence, especially on Europe. Discourse on the issue emerged, at least in part, as a result of concern about, and the study of, America ’ s influence on Europe. While after WW II the US was seen as the savior (at least by some) of Europe, by the 1960s it was perceived more as a business, industrial, and economic threat to Europe. More recently, the industrial threat posed by the US was replaced by a fear of American dominance in global consumption. Apart from the economic realm, the process of Americanization is also evident in Europe, and throughout the world, in such areas as politics, law, the military, and culture.

Appraisal of the Concept of Globalization in Developing Countries

Globalization is a rapidly ongoing phenomenon that generates a constant debate on both its positive and negative aspects. Some argue that globalization is a positive development that will enable the establishment of new industries and more jobs in developing and under developed countries. On the other hand, some opine that the concept of globalization have negative implications as it will compel poorer countries of the world to do whatever the developed states dictate to them. The lines between those who support globalization and its critics are not only between countries but within them as well. The debate about the true nature of globalization has divided people in the third world countries since this phenomenon occurred. It is now a matter of debate across the globe. Those that argue in support of globalization are right that international economic, political, cultural, technological and social integration is not only good for the poor countries, it is indeed, essential as no country can develop long-term without trade and globalization.

To start with, Miroslav and Sonja (2009) posit that globalization as a concept has positive and negative effects and consequences, the most important being: technological (spread of

information technology): political (strengthening of pre-national institutions and neutralization of national sovereignty and borders):economic (domination of multinational companies and widening the gap between developed - undeveloped): cultural (standardization of world culture): social (destruction of traditional system of values and worldwide Americanization). Indeed, critics and opponents of globalization insist it is a curse, and according to them: globalization brings benefits only to economically developed countries, international financial institutions and that instead of encouraging, impede economic development of developing countries as the gap between the rich and poor is constantly increasing. Moreover, developing countries do not have a developed network of institutions (legal, political,economic), which are necessary for the growth of market economy and equal participation in the process of globalization. To this end, the positive and negative touch points of globalization in relation to developing nations are presented thus:-

- **Technology and Globalization:** The most visible areas of societal functioning impacted by globalization are the large number of technological artifacts that are now part of day-to-day living. Technological changes of all sorts have played a huge role in globalization. Such changes have affected global processes for several decades.

The phenomenon of globalization has become possible primarily because of the advances that have taken place in science and technology, resulting in major disruptive technologies across a range of areas. The invention of the jet engine and a series of innovations that have brought about major changes in the scale of transportation modes has led to the ability to move people and goods using wide-bodied jet aircraft, giant ocean-going vessels, containerised transport and pipeline systems. Communication has been enhanced through the use of broadband telecommunication channels. This has been made possible through fibre optics and laser technology, satellites, and wireless communications, all based on scientific discoveries (over the last century) and related technologies (Menon, 2006).

Today, technology has the power to connect every one of the six billion individuals that constitute the population of the globe. The power of this connectivity on the human psyche and the areas of social interaction are truly profound. For instance, information technology has resulted in wholly new ways of communication such as digital storage and retrieval of all

types of information, call centres, business process outsourcing and so on. These technological aids have entered our lives in the last century; and in the present form, in just the last few decades. Now, life revolves round services like fax, xeroxing, e-mail, search on the World Wide Web, ATMs, and instantaneous communications at any time and at any place. The tempo of life associated with this usage has now become commonplace affecting a large part of human society. Furthermore, this capability has meant that financial resources can be transferred on an almost instantaneous basis, thus transforming the economy. The current competitive edge of economies is increasingly sourced from technical innovations and competitive use of knowledge than from the abundance of the traditional productive resources. In short, globalization helps for the flow of technology from advanced countries to the developing countries thereby helping the developing countries to implement new technology. The varying possibilities of technological inventions are part of positive outcomes of globalization for better productivity, social welfare and economic well being.

- **Media, Technology and Globalization:** In addition, globalization has enormously increased the power of the media. Through these communication channels, one can move data from any one point to any other point on the Earth. The data can be instantaneously processed and analyzed on computers, then displayed on screens of computers, mobile phones, television sets and the like. People and goods are moved at speeds that are still tangible; but data (e.g. bits) can be moved at the speeds of electrons and electromagnetic waves. Through globalization, the media landscape aided by technology has transformed greatly from the crude mode of transmission and the black and white equipment to improved operations including the use of sophisticated gadgets such as drone.
- **Education and Globalization:** In academic cycles and education, globalization has brought about connectivity among scholars all over the world through international conferences, symposia, workshops, trainings, scholarships, academic social networking sites like research gate, academia and so on. Also, there is unlimited access to wide volume of information. This has promoted research, scholarly writings in various disciplines. Globalization has also enthroned global competitiveness in the academic curriculum and modules of educational institutions at elementary, basic and tertiary levels. This revolution has created a global village and the emergence of the concept of a knowledge society. With globalization and explosion in information and communications technology, knowledge is not only expanding exponentially, it is now

easily accessible across the globe due to the rapid developments in information and communications technology (ICT). This has hastened and strengthened the linkages of universities, research institutions, scientists and other individuals in the knowledge industry. (PASCN 2003: 10).

- **Globalization and Economic Activities:** A major effect of globalization is the conduct of economic activity on a global basis without any reference to national boundaries. Economically, globalization has brought about increasing interdependence of national economies across the world through the rapid increase in the cross-border movement of goods, services, manpower, technology and capital. Globalization fosters economic liberalization in terms of foreign direct investment (FDI). This explains why developing countries like Nigeria try as much as possible to create enabling environment to woo foreign investors that cut across all sectors; oil and gas, manufacturing, petro-chemicals, agriculture, construction, telecommunications, conglomerates and the likes. For instance, in India, business process outsourcing has been described as the primary engine of the country's development over the next few decades, contributing broadly to GDP growth, employment growth, and poverty alleviation. Similarly, Chinese economic reform began to open China to the globalization in the 1980s. in fact, China has attained the degree of openness that is unprecedented among the large and populous nations", with competition from foreign goods in almost every sector of the economy. Foreign investment helped to greatly increase quality, knowledge and standards, especially in heavy industry. China's experience supports the assertion that globalization greatly increases wealth for poor countries. As of 2005-2007, the Port of Shanghai holds the title as the World's busiest port (Essays, 2013). In Nigeria, the nation's foreign investment stood at \$98 billion as at 2016. Correspondingly, with foreign investors, employment opportunities are available for the citizenry. In Nigeria for example, the likes of Mobile Telecommunication Network (MTN), Julius Berger Nigeria, Vasvani Brothers, Stallion group, Mobil, BBC, Chevron and other multinational companies have a good number of Nigerians in their workforce. It also encourages globalization of production, markets, competition, technology, and corporations and industries. Current globalization trends can be largely accounted for by developed economies integrating with less developed economies, by means of foreign direct investment, the reduction of trade barrier as well as other economic reforms and, in many cases, immigration. Further, the discussions now relate

not only to physical trade but also various other aspects of economic activity that are relevant to the deeper economic integration of countries: as regards finances, investments, services, technology. For example, if any country places undue restrictions on free trade in any of these areas, in violation of international agreements, it will be liable to sanction. Moreover, debt relief from Paris Club and foreign aids given to developing countries e.g. Nigeria by donor agencies in developed countries like Unicef, WHO dedicated towards development activities in less developed countries through Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs) is also an offshoot of the economic benefits of globalization.

- **Globalization and Cultural Practices:** Globalization has brought about cultural exchange across the globe and demand for a variety of products or perhaps what is called hybridization of cultural flows. The cultural hybridization approach emphasizes the integration of local and global cultures. Therefore, globalization turns people's culture to a creative process that involves integrating new teachings and knowledge about other cultures into one's own cultural practices. Put succinctly, globalization has reduced the physical distance among the countries thus enabling people of different countries to acquire the culture of other countries in terms of dressing, feeding, speaking, greeting, socialization, cultural norms and practices. The cultural exchange, in turn makes the people to demand for a variety of products which are being consumed in other countries. An example, foreign dishes are being introduced to Nigerian routine dishes and menu. In fact, some of the traditional meals are now being cooked and served with some western technical know-hows; e.g. garnishing of Jollof rice with carrots and other vegetables, cake and *moi-moi* baking and the use of pounding machines for pounded yam to replace mortar and pestle, use of shirts, blazers, suits and so on instead of African traditional attire.
- **Globalization and Politics:** The political landscape and electoral processes are also positively affected by globalization across the globe. International politics, elections, governance, power play among nations have become issues of global concerns. Many tyrant leaders in developing countries have been checkmate by the world's power brokers, cases involving past African leaders like former presidents of Gambia and Zimbabwe; Yahya Jammeh and Robert Mugabe. As a matter of fact, many international bodies (like the International Criminal Court: ICC, International police: [Interpol]) have been formed to oversee and curb excesses of tyrant leaders especially in Africa.

Globalization has also brought about improvements in electoral process as most developing countries now imitate and implement electoral practices in advanced countries. This perhaps buttress why in African countries, the military can no longer hijack governance through coup de tat as witnessed in the 1060s and 1980s. Now, democratic processes have been enthroned up to the point of using card readers since 2015 and allowing international election observers in the Nigerian 2015 general elections.

Are Developing Countries Fairing Well?

In spite of the laudable impacts of globalization in developing and under developed countries, nonetheless, it also has its draw backs. The negative effects of globalization not only on the productive sectors of the economy but also on cultural, environment, health, education and society as a whole cannot be overlooked. Bordo (2002), notes that much of the criticism against globalization had to do with political interests, and the reaction by those negatively affected by new economic developments. It has been argued that in developing world, globalization has not brought the promised economic benefits. For instance, at the moment, a growing divide between the haves and the have-nots has left increasing numbers in the Third World in dire poverty, living on less than a dollar a day. Despite repeated promises of poverty reduction made over the last decade of the twentieth century, the actual number of people living in poverty has actually increased by almost 100 million. This occurred at the same time that total world income actually increased by an average of 2.5 percent annually. In Nigeria and by extension, Africa, the high aspirations following colonial independence have been largely unfulfilled. Instead, the continent plunge deeper into misery, as incomes and gross domestic product has been on the decline. Also, globalization encourages smuggling of some sort especially in countries with porous borders and ports like Nigeria.

- **Cross Border Crimes and Terrorism:** Negative global flows and processes such as dangerous imports, cross - border crime, terrorism, and war are aided by globalization as they are now perpetrated across borders with ease and at great speed. Globalization allows cross – border crimes such as flows of drugs trafficking, money laundering, kidnapping, human trafficking as well as illegal commodities, through physical as well as virtual (Internet - based) channels. It also allows terrorism. Terrorism are actions that can cause “deaths, serious bodily injuries, and serious damage to public or private property, places, facilities, or other systems”(Ritzer, 2011) and are aimed at intimidating citizens, governments, or international organizations. This is evident in the numbers of killings, and bombings recorded in the activities of ISIS, Al- Quaeda, *Boko haram* and the likes. In short, global interconnectedness implies that a

war in a region is no longer an isolated phenomenon and will involve other regions, often quite distant, directly or indirectly. Therefore, the economic gains of war and easy access to weapons in the global era might actually lead to an increase in warfare as advanced technologies make a new form of warfare, information war and possible production of weapon of mass destruction.

- **Cultural Distortions:** Cultural imperialism, wherein one culture imposes itself on and tends to destroy at least parts of another culture, is one major setback that globalization has brought into people's culture. The negative aspects arise when in the process of globalization many valuable aspects of earlier cultural forms of a social group, country or community such as dressing, greeting speaking, socialization including languages, are destroyed. For real, language is often looked upon as a technical device to communicate between two individuals and within social groups. As such, any language ultimately represents a way of life and a way of thinking in which many aspects of a community's environment and experiences are embedded. However, in Nigeria, most of the indigenous languages (Yoruba, Igbo, Hausa) are in extinction because English Language is now being seen as the first language in almost all families.
- **Cyber Crimes:** Activities of internet fraudsters are on the rise with globalization and technology. Notably among such illegal activities is the increase in ponzi schemes imported from other countries like e-money, MMM (from Russia), yahoo yahoo (Nigerian fraudsters) and the likes. Cyber crimes also includes fraudulent practices in form of damages to data bases and computer software, informatics sabotage, hacking, unauthorized interpreting and copying of computer software, damaging and unauthorized use of data (Nistor ,2007), intrusion of privacy by social media platforms like Facebook, Google adverts all in the name of web analytics and interactive marketing. Little wonder, the US congress summoned Mark Zuckerberg to explain the social media platform policy on users privacy recently.
- **Environmental and Health Hazards:** Globalization also contributes to the spread of diseases in some ways. It causes exposure to vulnerable diseases like HIV/AIDS, Ebola, lassa fever and so on contacted through migration of infected personnel into other countries. History will never forget Patrick Sawyer, a Liberian ambassador that brought Ebola disease to Nigeria and in the process killed Dr. Ameyo Adedavoh who got infected with Ebola virus while trying to prevent him from escaping from her hospital in Lagos in 2015. The spread of such diseases showcases the difficulty involved in checking the flow of disease -

causing pathogens across borders. This global spread is particularly influenced by the increasing mobility of people. (Ritzer, 2011). In addition, globalization also cause environmental degradation and pollution such as deforestation and bio chemical waste causing health hazards and diseases like cancer, inflammation and even deaths arising from inhaling carbon monoxides from generators, industrial machines and car exhausts. With globalization, the re-use of electrical, electronic equipment and gadgets already thrown away by first users in developed countries is paramount making some developing countries like Nigeria become dumping grounds for abandoned electronic gadgets/devices like laptops, computers, printers, cars, clothings and even some expired food items.

- **Intellectual Property Theft:** Globalization in education and knowledge sharing through the internet has encouraged plagiarism to a great extent due to access to information on the internet. Many researchers and scholars often download and use information without giving due credits to the originators of such works.
- **Lack of Adequate Basic Infrastructure:** Provision of economical and efficient infrastructure is essential for economic development. However, the responsibility of providing it remains essentially with the government of respective countries. Therefore, there is a risk that a poor country, which is not able to provide infrastructure for inviting foreign investment capital, may remain perpetually poor and suffer from inferior terms of trade in the bargain.
- **Money Laundering:** With globalization, corrupt leaders and individuals especially Africans and Nigerians in particular launder funds meant for the economical, social-political development of their countries and citizenry. Many money laundering cases under past regimes(both military and democratic) are still under investigation by the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission in Nigeria with names of looters recently published in Nigerian dailies.
- **Media Imperialism:** With globalization and liberalization of media ownership in Nigeria, various forms of unreal escapist entertainment and media contents have arisen through the overwhelming commercialization of the media leading to misleading the youths about lifestyles and value systems. In fact , With the emergence of a media imperialism through globalization, one begins to see a globalised, homogenized culture in relation to clothes, fashions, cuisines, question of morality attitudes to sex , drug abuse and the like.

- **Loss of Man Power in Developing Countries:** Globalization can cause highly skilled workers to migrate in search of greener pastures from their countries leading to loss of manpower in developing and under developed countries. A good number of Nigerians now live in other countries of the world (America, Canada, Australia, Turkey, London to mention a few). The migrants may leave their families and live temporarily in another country, thus disrupting the family and social fabric of their home countries. Furthermore, most of their earnings may be sent home, reducing the benefits their employment could have in the country where they are employed. Often foreign workers immigrate to another country and, because they live in their own neighbourhoods, continue to follow their religions, customs, and even follow their own laws, they are sometimes accused of not being willing to adapt and accept their new country. To Guogis (2013), globalization has made personal independent voice of an individual to lose its value and thereby is becoming meaningless. In fact, he argues that under the circumstances of globalization, uncontrolled situations emerge and not only threaten individuals, but also communities, entire social groups and, finally, national states. While it is true that certain situations threaten individual and the entire community, one however will not agree with Guogis' position that the personal independent voice of an individual has been lost to globalization. This is because, globalization and the advent of the new media has empowered the individual and given them platforms to express their voice and individuality especially through social networking sites.

Summary and Conclusion

The truth is, we live in an era of globalization – there can be no going back on it. Matters of fact, countries have little choice whether to globalize or not. However, many developing nations and scholars are of the opinion that globalization may lead to loss of control over economic, territorial and political decisions which may also threaten their tradition, language, culture and value systems.

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Bowen University Deployment of Corporate Social Responsibility and Crisis Management within Her Host Communities (2012 – 2015)

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Abstract

Crisis is a point of decision which if not handled in an appropriate manner may turn into a disaster or catastrophe. No organization is immune to crisis. Bowen University had its surfeiting dose of crisis with her host communities from 2012 - 2015. This study examined how Bowen University used corporate social responsibility (CSR) strategies as a crisis management tool to resolve the crisis. Survey method was adopted for the study and the populations Iwo and Olupona with a sample size of 203 respondents. Simple random, stratification and purposive sampling techniques were used to collect data for the study. The study answered four research questions: What are the grievances of the host communities? What are the natures of the crises? How did Bowen University resolve the crisis? How effective was the CSR strategies Bowen University used as a crisis management tool? Stakeholders' theory and the iron law of corporate social responsibility theory were used for the study. The study considered: the concept of CSR, CSR model, CSR in tertiary institutions, practicing University Corporate Social Responsibility (UCSR) as well as crisis management. Data gathered were analyzed using descriptive statistics and results were presented in tables and percentages. Three important findings emerged from this study. First, universities, particularly private ones should embrace CSR and cultivate the environment where they operate in order to be successful in a highly competitive educational industry. Second, Bowen University crisis from 2012 – 2015 was as a result of its inability to cultivate the environment where it operates. Thirdly, the CSR strategies used as a crisis management tool by the university to resolve the crisis were effective. The study concludes that tertiary institutions should cultivate the environment where they operate so as to enjoy the goodwill of the host community. The study recommends that tertiary institutions should corporatize to enable it meet the socio-political and economic challenges facing them, move away from depending on grants and subventions from its proprietors and become self-sustaining.

Key words: Corporate social responsibility, stakeholders, goodwill, university, crisis management

Word Count: 325

Introduction

According to Musa and Audu (2016), the activities of every organization significantly contribute to the well-being of its environment. Corroborating this assertion, Hashimu and Ango (2012) opine that the routine and administrative activities of organizations have direct or indirect impact to the stakeholders ranging from employees, customers, host communities, government and the general public. In a similar development, Igwe (2011) observes that the interactions between organization and its environment pose some social economic challenges that if not properly handled could adversely affect the smooth operations of the environment. Irrespective of these postulations, corporate social responsibility (CSR) has continued to face series of criticisms on the legitimacy or otherwise of its acceptance and subsequent application by organizations. Shehu (2013) confirmed this submission when he says that CSR like most concepts in the field of social and management sciences has been faced with controversies. He observes that the conceptual and theoretical dimensions of CSR have been viewed from economic, social, political, demographic and legal angles, resulting to perspective problems that lack uniformity in approach. It is the view of this researcher that this lack of uniformity in both perspective and approach led to the arguments and counter arguments on the appropriateness or otherwise of CSR. Deliberating on the genuineness of CSR as a means of achieving organizational objective is simply stating the obvious. Aligning with this submission, McWilliams (2006), cited in Aminu, Harashied and Azlam (2016) state that the transformation of CSR from an irrelevant or doubtful idea to an indispensable component in achieving organizational objectives has been recognized by managers and stakeholders. They state further that managers are using it as a tool to strategize, comply with regulations and maintain set standard, build corporate reputations and get more customer loyalty which all culminates in increasing profitability and overall attainment of organizational objective. The snag over the years had remained its subjection to legal compliance and equating it with philanthropic disposition.

The major problem of CSR had remained its definitional pluralism and conflictual conceptualization. Different scholars in different specialization defined CSR based on their professional and academic dimensions. Supporting this view, Amodu (2013) said that there is a definitional problem in CSR discourse. He states further that everybody talks about CSR and yet, nobody has been able to give a generally acceptable definition of the phenomenon. CSR is multidisciplinary. It caught across many scholars and experts in many fields and disciplines, with each scholar offering his own perspective on the subject. Buttressing the submission of Amodu, Carroll and Shabana (2010), cited in Baric (2017) point out that the concept of CSR represents an encompassing framework of different concepts that study the relationship of companies and the community in which the company operates regardless of whether the community is local, national or global. Because the concept is highly complex, there is no unanimously accepted definition of the concept of CSR to this day, so it is interpreted differently within the global economic network, and often by different groups of stakeholders.

Not minding the divergent views of scholars, professionals and stakeholders on the concept of CSR, the fact is that the importance of CSR in an organization cannot be over emphasized. Indeed, it is an inevitable tool in organizational sustenance, growth and development. Nielsen and Thomson (2009) cited in Baric (2017) corroborated this views when they posit that “even though the concept of CSR is highly complex, it also undoubtedly possesses a clear strategic determinant and represents an inseparable part of the business model of modern global corporations throughout the world today”. CSR supports the society as a way of compensation for the loss incurred as well as profit derived through organizational or business operations carried out in their environment. CSR as a tool of Public Relations is to create a favorable and conducive ambience for business to thrive. This is why Ajala (2005) observed that: “through corporate social responsibility, a company is able to provide a healthy business environment for its operations and contribute to the well-being of the community. Supporting Ajala’s view, Asogwa and Onuh (2014) opine that a key indicator to determine the true worth and value of modern organizations is their ability to give back to the society part of what they earn through some mutually beneficial initiatives. They states that these initiatives are captured in the concept of CSR. Asogwa (2014) sees CSR as a necessary ingredient needed to improve corporate image and continued peaceful coexistence between an organization and its communities. It is a recognizable tool for promoting mutual understanding and goodwill between an organization and the community it is operating in and the society at large.

CSR is so important and crucial that organizations now believe there is need to constantly and critically look at its role globally with a view to reviewing, standardizing and sustaining it for efficiency, effectiveness as well as creating a good image for organization. Asemah, Okpanachi and Olumuji (2013) aligned with this opinion when they state that the goodwill and corporate image of organization requires the instrumentality of CSR. According to them, this will not only promote productivity and efficient service delivery but also ensure peaceful co-existence within and outside the immediate environment. They posit further that this also applies to tertiary institutions considering its pivotal role to the development of education on one hand and the socio-economic development of the society on the other hand.

In the words of Sukaina and Kamal (2015), universities nowadays are faced with new environment and challenges that necessitate the need to be independent from government and state support. They assert that universities are moving toward corporatization which calls for them to be a good corporate citizen and the best approach for universities to achieve that is by adapting the concept of CSR. Supporting this view, Dahan and Senol (2012) aver that universities, especially private ones are in need of strong corporate strategies in order to be successful in the highly competitive education industry. They said that CSR had become one of the highly preferred strategies by higher education institutions for gaining a good reputation and a competitive advantage. It is equally a strategic tool in the ambiance of crisis resolution between an organization and its host community.

The thrust of this paper is to examine CSR as a crisis management tool and how Bowen University used it to resolve the crisis with its host communities from 2012-2015.

Statement of the Problem

The survival and growth of any business organization is largely dependent on the community or environment of such organization which consists of the interacting factors that can either make or mar it. Before now, Universities are not seen as organizations that are established for business purposes and so they tend not to embrace CSR (Asemah et al 2013). Tertiary institutions represent a vital body of the society and need to cultivate the environment where they operate in order to enjoy the goodwill of their host communities. To do otherwise is invitation of crisis. Bowen University handled some of the crisis with host communities from 2012 – 2013. This study investigated how Bowen University used CSR strategies as a crisis management tool to resolve the crisis between it and her host communities during the year under review.

Research Objectives

The objective of this study is to investigate the CSR programmes that Bowen University used as a crisis management tool to resolve the crises between the university and its host communities from 2012 -2015. The study among other things, seeks to find out:

- i. the grievances of the host communities;
- ii. the nature of the crises between Bowen University and its host communities from 2012 -2015;
- iii. efforts made by Bowen University to arrest the crises; and the effectiveness of the CSR strategies used by Bowen University as a crisis management tool to resolve the crisis?

Research Questions

1. What are the grievances of the host communities?
2. What are the nature of the crises between Bowen University and her host communities from 2012 - 2015?
3. What are the strategies deployed by Bowen University to resolve the crisis?
4. How effective were the CSR strategies Bowen University used as a crisis management tool?

Theoretical Framework

The importance of theories in a research cannot be over emphasized. In the words of Lewis (1958), cited in Amodu (2012), good theories enable researchers to put facts in perspectives and to hypothesize what will happen even before they happen. In the same vein, Folarin (2005), cited in Amodu (2012) avers that theories help researchers to manage realities. CSR as a crisis management tool has theoretical foundations. It is on this premise that stakeholders and iron law of responsibility theories were adopted for this study.

Stakeholders' Theory: The concept of stakeholders refers to groups whose support, the organization needs in order to remain in business. It was championed by Edward Freeman in the '80s. Asemah et al (2013) describes stakeholders' theory as a theory of organizational management and business ethics that addresses morals and values in managing an organization. Stakeholders' theory focuses on the principle of whom or what really counts in an organization. In the context of CSR, stakeholders' theory is based on the assumption that organizations have obligations to the groups that make up the environment where it operates. These constituents are referred to as stakeholders. They are individuals and groups that are critical to the existence of the organization.

They influence what the organization does and are also influenced by the actions of the organization. Stakeholders' theory is of the view that management has a moral duty to protect both the corporation and the legitimate interest of the stakeholders. It implies therefore that organization should invest in the society where it is situated. When this is done, the organization will reap in form of improved reputation and understanding when things go wrong. This theory is relevant to this study because it explains the constituent that organization should be responsible to. Alam (2015) in supporting this view affirms that companies that are socially responsible to the constituent groups will win their goodwill and this will in turn impact on the operations of the company positively.

Iron law of Social Responsibility Theory: W.C. Frederick propounded the theory of iron law of social responsibility in 1960. According to him, "social responsibilities of businessmen need to commensurate with their social power". The iron law of social responsibility theory explains the negative consequences of organizational failure to be socially responsible. It could be deduced from this theory that any organization that fails to cultivate the environment they operate will undoubtedly face the wrath of the environment by way of strike, protest, litigations, picketing, sanctions, willful destruction of properties and other related avoidable hostilities that will hamper their operations. This is possible because according Moon (2002) cited in Aminu et al (2016), CSR has gained an institutional status for regulators because of its legal linkage with compliance to law and ethical practices which empowers societies to take actions against organizations that refused to cultivate the environment where they operate. The iron law of social responsibility states that in the long run, those companies that do not use power in ways that society consider responsible will tend to lose. Companies are attached to the environment based on the iron low of social responsibility. Companies must be socially responsible to the people where they operate (Alam 2015). This theory is considered relevant to this study because it lays emphasis on the need for organizations to be socially responsible in order to be able to win the goodwill of stakeholders and avoid hostilities that brings disharmony between the organization and its host community.

Conceptual Framework

Ayandele (2002), cited in Abu Karim and Audu (2016) sees social responsibility (SR) as a form of self-regulation, conscious attempts and self-efforts carried out by organizations to sustain self-preservation and promotion of harmonious co-existence. Corroborating this view, Odetayo, Adeyemi and Sajuyigbe (2014) note that CSR also known as corporate conscience or social performance is seen as operational mechanism whereby organizational activities are carried out by responding positively to societal priorities and expectations with the commitment to meet the ethical standard of the society and the organization.

In the same vein, Ikporukpo (2001) states that environment is totally human surroundings. Reacting in the same direction, Osibanjo (1998), cited in Abu Karim et al (2016), views environment as man immediate surroundings. Because organizations cannot operate in a vacuum, it is right to say that their activities depend largely on interaction with the environment where they operate. As a result, harmonizing the interests of such organizations and that of the society can only be achieved through the mechanism of CSR. In line with this, that World Economic Forum (2003) argued that corporate citizenship which is synonymous with CSR is the contributions and other conscious efforts carried out by organizations through compliance to ethical business activities, social investment, philanthropic activities and other social or community efforts to improve the well-being of the citizens within the environment.

Analyzing a broader approach to the conceptualization of CSR, Justin and Wadike (2013), identified four distinctive dimensions which CSR should adopt such as: economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic. According to them, these dimensions must be fulfilled for the mutual benefits of organization and its immediate environment. CSR can only be successful if these dimensions are properly harnessed, analyzed and implemented within the framework of consciousness that will create a balance between the organization and its stakeholders. Supporting this opinion, Sun et al (2010) aver that within the concept of CSR, stakeholders are portrayed as groups of persons towards whom the company's activities are oriented. Today, according to them, it is almost impossible to discuss the concept of CSR without taking note of the stakeholders of the company.

CSR Model: A model is a physical representation that shows what something is, how it looks like and how it works. Therefore, corporate social responsibility model is a physical representation that shows what CSR is, how it looks like and how it works. Andy Carroll is one of the foremost theorists of CSR. He identified four different kinds of organizational responsibilities. They are economic, legal, ethical as well as philanthropic responsibilities. Carroll (1991) made a distinction between these organizational responsibilities according to their hierarchy of needs. This distinction in the context of CSR is referred to as firm's "pyramid of CSR.

Fig. 1 Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Source: Carroll's (1991) CSR Pyramid

Carroll sees business as a basic economic unit in the society and has a responsibility that is economic in nature. According to him, economic responsibility is the most fundamental responsibility of an organization. This is because it reflects the essence of a firm as a profit making organization. Economic responsibility implies that society expects organization to produce goods and services as demanded by the society and make profit as a reward. The legal responsibility refers to expectations of legal compliance by the organization. It means playing by the rules of the game. Jamali (2008) puts it more succinctly when he states that “from legal perspective, society expects business to fulfill its economic mission within the framework set forth by the society’s legal system”. Aligning with this postulation, Crane and Matten (2007), cited in Baric (2017) further add that all companies attempting to be socially responsible are required to follow the law. In the same vein, Schwart (2001), cited in Sukaina and Kamal (2015) explain that the ethical responsibilities embody those standards, norms, or expectations that reflect a concern for what consumers, employees, shareholders and the community regard as fair, just in keeping with the respect or protection of the stakeholders’ moral right. Philanthropic responsibilities represent the smallest layer of the pyramid. It involves the organization’s willingness to enhance the quality of living of their stakeholders through charitable donations and organizational support that is entirely voluntary and serves as desirable by the society.

Based on these, it is expected of organizations, tertiary institutions inclusive to be economically responsible, play by the rules of the game and demonstrate an appreciable level of voluntariness to the society, particularly its host communities in order to ensure healthy competitiveness and lasting sustainability within local and global index. This is why

Vasilescu, Barna, Epure and Baicu (2010), cited in Sukaina and Kamal (2015) say that “social responsibility (SR) has become an increasingly important concept globally and it has become part of the debate about competitiveness and sustainability in the context of globalization

CSR in Tertiary Institutions

Before now, CSR is seen as an activity that concern only organizations that operate solely on profit maximization and therefore had to cultivate their environment and win the goodwill of their stakeholders if they want to remain in business. Universities are not seen to be concerned with CSR. Scholars focused their CSR studies majorly on multi-national corporations with little or no studies on CSR of universities and other related tertiary institutions. Affirming this position, Asemah, Okpanachi and Olumuji (2013) say that universities are often not seen as organizations that are established for business purpose and so they tend not to embrace CSR. But contrary to this, however, present day socio-political and economic realities requires that universities and other tertiary institutions need to carry out CSR so as to win the goodwill of their stakeholders. Evidently, universities that cultivate their environment and live up to their corporate social responsibilities will as a matter of fact, enjoy the goodwill of their host communities. This is why university social responsible (USR) had become imperative in these days that universities are faced with daunting challenges of reputational building and socio-economic and educational sustainability. Corroborating this view Reiser, (2008), cited in Sukaina and Kamal (2015) define University Social Responsibility (USR) concept as a policy of ethical quality of the performance of the university community (students, faculty, and administrative employees) via the responsible management of the educational, cognitive, labour and environmental impacts produced by the university, in an interactive dialogue with society to promote a sustainable human development.

It should be observed from these submissions that tertiary institutions represent a vital body of any society and as such are faced with new environments and daunting challenges that call for independent from government and organizational support. Daxner and Ivošević (2007), Felt (2003), and Eckstein (2003), cited in Sukaina (2015) supported this view when they identified the changing environment that universities function and the challenges that higher institutions face as follows: mass expansion, decrease of governmental/public expectations and support for universities, diversification of financial resources, internationalization, commercialization and increase in the entrepreneurial character of institutions, challenges brought by societal expectations etc. Felt 2003 and Vasilescu (2010) both agree that these issues will impact on the quality of education, university autonomy, academic freedom, the changing focus on academic and university’s responsibilities towards society. It is their view that to meet these crucial and inevitably daunting challenges, universities should corporatize. University corporatization requires that they become socially responsible. University social responsibility (USR), according to Vasilescu et al, (2010) and Shawyun (2011) encompasses many different areas including the need to strengthen civil commitment and active citizenship to provide services to the community through community engagement and outreach, to promote economic and national development, to promote ethical

approaches to issues, to develop a sense of civil citizenship by encouraging the students, academic and administrative staff to provide social services to their community, to promote ecological or environmental commitment for local and global sustainable knowledge through quality research and education for the nation and for humanity.

Similarly, Gumport (200) cited in Gresi and Isil (2012) state that following decades of world war II, higher educational institutions acknowledged that the activities regarded as the legitimate province of public higher education was changed such as educating the masses, advancing knowledge through research, contributing to economic development by employing workers and developing industrial application. The universal socio-political and economic meltdown has changed this narrative. It is obvious from these postulations that it is now more of survival of the fittest today in terms of tertiary institutions' development and sustainability. More reasons universities and other related tertiary institutions fast embracing the option of UCSR. Supporting this, Weymmas (2010), said "the message for the academia is clear: academia is not allowed to lock themselves up in the ivory tower anymore". The charge to tertiary institutions today for development and sustainability is clear without any iota of ambiguity.

Globalization has embraced tertiary institutions and universities had begun to experience a significant paradigm shift from government funding and organizational subventions. Gone are days when academic institutions were allowed to act in a self-contained manner and thrive in an environment of predictable funding with little overt competition among institutions. But now, due to the high globalization index, educational institutions are facing keen competition in order to attract high quality academic and non-academic staff with an encouraging student enrolment within national and international borders.

This is a clear indication that university administration and management has moved away from the old fashioned method of confining itself to the classroom waiting for grants or subventions from their proprietors to a dynamic, resourceful and result-oriented institutions that are both entrepreneurial and technologically driven with sound ethical and social responsibilities base-line. The only way out of this seemingly quagmire is for universities and related tertiary institutions to embrace this inevitable change and begin to operate in a business-like manner. This is why Weymmas (2010) said "since it is not possible to turn back the clock in this globalized post-national world, there is no alternative but to reform universities by making them more adapted to new economic realities". This adaption in the context of this study is to allow universities and other related tertiary institutions operate in a business-like manner. If universities and tertiary institutions start to behave in a business-like manner, it is imperative that they be managed in the same way. This will make implementation of UCSR a prerogative of universities and tertiary institutions to enable them gain a competitive advantage and positive reputation. Corroborating this view, Gresi and Isil (2012) aver that universities, especially private ones are in need of strong corporate strategies in order to be successful in the highly competitive educational industry. According to them,

in order to be ahead of their competitors, private universities are in search of sustainable differentiating strategies such as UCSR.

Practicing University Corporate Social Responsibility (UCSR)

University leadership determines how its corporate social responsibilities can be carried out. Sukaina and Kamal (2015) agree with this view when they aver that UCSR can be put into practice when university leaders emphasize on the importance of social responsibility to the public, ethical behavior and the need to practice good citizenship. According to them, it is expected that university leaders should be role models on ethics, protection of community health, safety and environment. In the context of this paper, university leaders are the policy makers of university. They include the visitor, pro-chancellor, members of the governing council, vice-chancellor, principal officers, senate, management and the congregation of the university. These are the policy makers and policy implementers of university. UCSR is a policy as well as managerial function of university. Its operational methodology is determined by these categories of people. It behooves on management therefore to come up with appropriate and acceptable CSR that the university will embark upon in line with the prevailing circumstances of her host community. It is this gesture that will create a conducive atmosphere and enabling environment for the university to operate with peace and harmony that will in turn, enhance productivity, goodwill and the reputation of the university.

To practice UCSR refers to supporting issues that are important to the public and contribute to the wellbeing of the society, though within the limits and resources of the university. Sukaina and Kamal (2015) identified those issues to include, improving education in the community, performing community services, conducting research to generate socio-economic development and providing guidelines for development and sustainability of the society. They opine that universities can also influence other organizations and institutes, whether private or public to form partnerships for addressing these issues and concerns. Furthermore, they gave example of Hashemite University Jordan (HUI) which had motivated scholars and scientists with a shared dedication for the quest of knowledge, value of community services and the importance of dialogue for a stable flourishing society. In the same vein, Sokratis et al (2011), cited in Gresi and Isil (2012), state that Istanbul Bilgi University (IBU), Japan, starting from its establishment, committed itself to the propagation of democratic values and human rights, to critical thought and effective intervention in the social fabric of its multi-cultural environment. According to them, IBU sustainably continued to create a cultural and scientific environment that has strong ties with every part of the society, managed to apply a successful UCSR strategy and gained a good reputation as well as a strong competitive advantage. In a similar development, Abu Karim and Audu (2016) affirm that the Federal Polytechnic, Idah, Kogi state, over the years, has been committed to various stakeholders through CSR such as admission policy which considered mostly indigenes and candidates from the immediate community, provision of pipe-borne water, employment opportunities and award of contracts to the immediate community etc, has been able to promote mutual understanding in the institution with its host community. Practicing

UCSR requires the approval of the policy makers while appropriate recommendations will be made by the university management. This calls for a proper and enhanced channel of communication between the authorities. To achieve this requires adequate CSR governance and cohesion between the university management and the policy makers. Du et al (2011), cited in Baric (2017) aligned with this assertion when he postulates that by adequate governance of the concept of CSR, the management can achieve better financial result and at the same time, improve the community in which it operates by increasing the standard of living of the company's internal and external stakeholders. From these explanations, it could be inferred that the application of UCSR paves way for harmonious relationship between tertiary institutions and its host communities which resultant effect is the creation of goodwill and reputation building. The opposite is an invitation of hostility with a corresponding crisis which needs to be properly managed by the university. UCSR can only be effective if the university understands the community where it operates.

Crisis Management

Academic and managers identified crisis as a critical event or a point of decision which if not handled in an appropriate and timely manner may turn into a disaster or catastrophe (Business Dictionary, 2015). The risks associated with these are real and the organizations facing a crisis are at stake. One significant point to note is that no organization is immune to crisis. What matters most is the ability to respond to it timely and appropriately. Regester and Larkin (2005), cited in Andrea (2015), in supporting this view note that "it is not important how organizations are well organized and established, rich of any applicable procedures and practices or over-controlled by experienced management, unwanted event may happened any time to jeopardize the organization itself and the business". It is therefore, important to define and articulate strategies and procedures to manage and limit crisis when it comes in the most effective and efficient manner. In this wise, leaders of organization play important role in the case of unforeseen event such as crises.

According to Vassilikopoulou, Lepeteos, Simkos and Chatzipanagiotu (2009), cited in Business Dictionary (2015), there are four factors that contribute to the perception of crisis by management. They include but not limited to: company reputation and social responsibility, company response to the crisis, the magnitude of the crisis in terms of damage, external effect such as media coverage and communication strategy. Leaders and managers of organization are saddled with the responsibility to handle these factors. This is because they are the only ones that has the power and authority to: (a) provide policies and strategies that will promote company reputation through the development of organizational culture; (b) guide the response of the company to the crisis; (c) provide the necessary resources to prevent the loss or reduce its magnitude as low as reasonably possible; and (d) communicate efficiently and effectively inside and outside the organization. Leaders of organization use two critical tools to manage crisis: communication and CSR.

Communication is a key element that organizations use to control or limit the damage done to organization through crisis. Organization should focus more on communication in

order to reduce the information asymmetry with the audience. Effective communication strategy will satisfy audience expectation and accelerate their recovery of broken trust which will in effect, protect organization's reputation and value. This requires that the media relations of the organization should be sound and nearly perfect. The importance of media in reputation building and crisis management in an organization cannot be over emphasized. Corroborating this assertion, Babaleye (2013) said "the media is the lamp and mirror through which organization can see itself and also get the reflection of how it is seen by its various publics". It therefore goes to say that the media can make or mar an organization. It can create crisis for an organization and can also help organization to resolve crisis. This ambivalent nature of the media puts it in a vantage position in any organization. The media is one of the important publics of organization. Crisis management can only be effective if there is a cordial relationship between the media and the organization. Crisis communication planning will help organization to deal effectively with those unexpected disaster, emergencies or unusual events that may cause unfavorable publicity. This is why Public Relations Society of America identified tactics and strategies of crisis management to include:

- (i) Bringing the situation under control. Always protect people first and property second. Analyze the situation to judge its newsworthiness. Do not create a crisis by jumping the gun. Many times, the situation does not warrant media attention;
- (ii) Gather the facts – who, what, where, when, why how and what next.
- (iii) If necessary, activate your crisis management team. Act quickly, spare no expense to distribute the information, determine the media to use.
- (iv) Give the media as much information as possible. They will get the information perhaps inaccurate from other sources.
- (v) Do not speculate. If you do not know the facts, say so and promise to get back to the media as soon as possible and be sure you do.
- (vi) Protect the integrity and reputation of the organization.
- (vii) Report your own bad news. Do not allow other sources to inform the media first.
- (viii) Perform an act of goodwill during or immediately after the crisis when appropriate and possible.

CSR is another critical element that organization uses to manage crisis. This is evidenced by Public Relations Society of America on point number 8 which states that "organization should perform an act of goodwill during or immediately after crisis when appropriate". Application of the appropriate CSR strategies will help organization to resolve crisis and rebuild broken relationship between organization and its publics, particularly the stakeholders. Timing of the reaction is crucial when organization is using CSR strategies to resolve crisis. These put together can only be possible if there is cordial relationship between the institutions and their host communities. Cordial relationship can only be practicable between tertiary institutions and their host communities when the community relations are properly cultivated and made functional through the application of appropriate corporate social responsibility tactics.

Research Methodology

This study adopted survey research design. This was to enable the researcher reach a sizeable of people within the target population. The method was thought to be appropriate because the research is people-oriented. The study population is made up of male and female residents of Iwo and Olupona communities in Iwo and Ayedire Local Government Areas of Osun state. The two communities are the host of Bowen University and the beneficiaries of its CSR. The sample size for this study is 203 respondents drawn from Iwo, Olupona and Bowen University respectively. The sample consists of 100 respondents each from Iwo and Olupona through questionnaire (200) and 1 respondent each from Iwo, Olupona and Bowen University through interview (3), making a total of 203 respondents. The study used three sampling techniques; simple random, stratification and purposive sampling techniques. Each of these techniques was used based on their attribute and relevance to the nature of the samples required from this population. 203 respondents from Iwo and Olupona communities were randomly selected for the study.

The two communities were stratified into two major strata based on the status of the members. Thus, we have opinion leaders/elders stratum and youths/matured adults' stratum. A simple random technique was used to select the respondents. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the structured interview subject. Purposive sampling technique was chosen because it will enable the researcher to select respondents that have adequate and informed knowledge of the phenomenon. Data collected for the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics with simple percentage. Results were discussed and presented in tables and percentages. The results were used to answer the research questions. Furthermore, the open ended questions in the interview schedules were analyzed through the identification of the respondent's views that are related to the research questions. They were explained based on their relevance and appropriateness to the research questions where necessary.

Results and Findings

Research Question One: What are the grievances of the host communities?

Table 1: Grievances of the Host Communities

No	Grievances	Frequently Aware		Rarely Aware	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	Inadequate monetary compensation for the acquisition of the land that belong to the indigenes of host communities by Bowen University.	120	60	80	40
2	Bowen University’s insensitivity towards community development projects.	160	80	40	20
3	Failure of Bowen University to fulfill her promises to the host communities.	108	54	92	46
4	Delay of intervention when there is need by host communities	110	55	90	45
5	Demand for employment and award of contracts to indigenes of the host communities.	82	41	118	59

Source: Field work, 2019

Table 1 shows that 60% of the respondents were frequently aware of Bowen University’s inadequate compensation to the land owners, 40% were rarely aware of it. 80% of the respondents were frequently aware of the insensitivity of Bowen University towards community development projects in her host communities while 20% were rarely aware of it. 54% were frequently aware of the failure of Bowen University to provide some basic social amenities to her host communities while 46% were rarely aware of it. 55% were frequently aware of Bowen University’s delay to intervene when there is need by her host communities while 45% are rarely aware of it. 59% were frequently aware of the demand for employment and award of contracts to the indigenes of her host communities while 41% were rarely aware of it.

Research Question Two: What are the nature of the crises between Bowen University and her host communities from 2012 -2015?

Table 2: Nature of the Crises between Bowen University and her Host Communities (2012 -2015)

No	Crises	Frequently Aware		Rarely Aware	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	Litigation on land acquisition and compensation in 2012	136	68	64	32
2	The Press release and protest by host communities against the inadequate compensation on the acquisition of their land in 2013.	180	90	20	10
3	The demand for employment by Youths of the host communities community in 2014	130	65	70	35
4	The protest against step-down of electricity supply from Ejigbo in 2015	150	75	50	25
5	The demand for employment and award of contracts to indigenes by youths and elders of the host communities.	38	19	162	81

Source: Field work 2019

Table 2 shows that 68% of the respondents are frequently aware of the court litigation on land acquisition and inadequate compensation by Bowen University in 2012 while 32% are rarely aware. 90% of the respondents are frequently aware of press releases and protests by Iwo and Olupona communities against the inadequate compensation on the acquisition of their land by Bowen University in 2013 while 10% were rarely aware of it. 65% of respondents were frequently aware of the demand for employment by youths of the host communities in 2014 while 35% were rarely aware of it. 75% of the respondents were aware of the protest against the step-down of electricity supply from Ejigbo in 2015 while 25% were not aware of it. 81% of the respondents were frequently aware of the demand youths and elders of the host communities for the award of contracts and scholarship to indigenes by Bowen University while 19 % were rarely aware of it.

Research Question There: What are the strategies deployed by Bowen University to resolve the crisis?

Table 3: Crisis Management Strategies Deployed by Bowen University

No	Corporate Social Responsibilities	Frequently Aware		Rarely Aware	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	Award of Scholarship to the students of the host communities	110	55	90	45
2	Employment and award of contracts to indigenes of the host communities	184	92	16	8
3	Sinking of boreholes and electrification of Oloya Village	186	93	14	7
4	Construction of Yidi Oba culvert	120	60	80	40
5	Participated in the building of Police Community Relations Committee (PCRC) Hall at the Divisional Headquarters, Adeeke, Iwo.	70	35	130	65
6	Reconstruction of the School of the blind building at the New Garage, Adeeke, Iwo.	180	90	50	10
7	Participated in the reconstruction and renovation of Oluwo Palace	140	80	60	20
8	Sand-filling of roads in the host communities	110	55	90	45
9	Monetary donations towards community development project.	112	56	88	44
10	Others (specify)	116	58	84	42

Source: Field work, 2019

Table 3 shows that 55% of respondents were frequently aware of the scholarships awarded to students of host communities by Bowen University between 2012 -2015 while 45% were rarely aware of it. 92% of the respondents were frequently aware of employment and award of contracts to indigenes of host communities of Bowen University between the years under review while 8% of the respondents were rarely aware of it. 93% of the respondents were aware of sinking of boreholes and electrification of Olooya Village in Olupona in 2015 while 7% of the respondents were not aware. 60% of respondents were aware of the construction of Yidi Oba culvert in Iwo also in 2015 while 40% were not aware. 35% of respondents were aware of Bowen University's participation in the building of Police Community Relations Hall at the Police Divisional Headquarters, Adeke, Iwo, in 2014 while 65% were not aware. 90% of respondents were aware of the reconstruction of the School of the Blind building at New Garage, Adeke, Iwo by Bowen University in 2013 while 10% of the respondents were not aware. 80% of the respondents were aware of the Bowen University participation in the reconstruction and renovation of Oluwo Place while 20% were not aware. 55% were frequently aware of the sand filling of bad roads in the host communities by Bowen University during the years under review while 45% were not aware. 58% of the respondents were frequently aware of other specific projects done by Bowen University to its host communities while 42% were rarely aware.

Research Question Four: How effective were the CSR strategies Bowen University used as a crisis management tool to resolve the crisis?

Table 4: Effectiveness of CSR strategies deployed by Bowen University to Resolve the Crisis

No	Impact	Frequently Aware		Rarely Aware	
		Frequen cy	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	Financial assistance/scholarship to students.	110	55	90	45
2	Contributing large sum of money to education tax fund	190	95	10	05
3	Construction of Yidi Oba culvert	180	90	20	10
4	Sinking of boreholes and electrification of Oloya Village	190	95	10	05
5	Cash donations in support of various community development efforts particularly in Iwo and Ayedire Local Government Areas	112	56	88	44

Source: Field work 2019

Table 4 shows that 55% of the respondents were frequently aware of financial assistance /scholarship to students of the host communities by Bowen University while 45% were rarely aware of it. 95% of respondents were frequently aware of contribution to educational tax fund by Bowen University while 5% were rarely aware of it. 90% of the respondents are aware of the construction of YidiObad Culvert by the University while 10% are not aware. 95% of the respondents are aware of the sinking of borehole and electrification of Olooya Village by the university while 5% of the respondents were not aware. 56% of the respondents are aware of the cash donations by the university to support the provision of some basic social amenities embarked upon by the host communities while 44% of the respondents are not aware.

Discussion of Findings

On the grievances of the host communities, respondents in table 1 shows that they were aggrieved because of inadequate monetary compensation for their land that Bowen University acquired, University's insensitivity towards community development, failure to provide some basic essential social amenities by the university, delay in intervention of the social needs of the host communities as well as non – employment, award of contracts and scholarships to indigenes of the host communities. 60%, 80%, 54%, 55% and 59% were frequently aware of the grievances while 40%, 20%, 46%, 45% and 41% were rarely aware. This shows that majority of the respondents are aware of the grievances of the host communities. These grievances are evidences that Bowen University did not cultivate the environment where they operate. This is contrary to the concept of CSR which established that organizations should cultivate the environment where they operate in order to enjoy the goodwill of the community. This tallied with the submission of Asemah et al (2013) which stipulates that universities that cultivate their environment and live up to their social responsibilities will as a matter of reciprocity, enjoy the goodwill of their host community.

Concerning the nature of the crisis table2showsthat 68% of the respondents are aware of the litigation on land acquisition and inadequate monetary compensation by the university while 32% were not aware. 75% of the respondents were aware of the protest of host communities against the step-down of electricity supply from Ejigbo in 2015 while 25% were not aware. 65% of respondents were frequently aware of the demand from the university in 2014 for employment, award of contracts and scholarships to indigenes of the host communities by the youths while 35% were not aware. 90% of respondents were frequently aware of the several press releases and protests by youths of the host communities against the university from 2012 – 2015 on the inadequate monetary compensation of their acquired land by the university while 10% were not frequently aware. Reports from the structured interview also confirmed that there were litigations, protests and physical attacks to Bowen University from the host communities.

Again, this shows that majority of the respondents are aware of the nature of the crisis between the university and her host communities. It also shows that the university is not socially responsible to her host communities. The crisis between Bowen University and her host communities are in tandem with the assumption of the iron law of corporate social responsibility theory by W.C. Frederick which explains the negative consequences of organizational failure to be socially responsible to include but not limited to: physical attack, protest, litigation, picketing, sanction, among other punitive measures. Concerning, strategies deployed by Bowen University to resolved the crisis, 55%, 92%, 93%, 60%, 90%, 80%, 55%, 56% and 58% of the respondents were frequently aware that Bowen University attended to the grievances of its host communities while 45%, 8%, 7%, 40%, 65%, 10%, 20%, 45%, 44% and 42% were rarely aware.

Table 3 shows that majority of the respondents are aware that the university have attended to the grievances of her host communities such as award of scholarships, contracts and employment to indigenes of host communities, sinking of boreholes, electrification of Olooya village, construction of culvert at Yidi Oba, participation in the building of PCRC Hall at Divisional Police Headquarters, Adeke, Iwo, reconstruction of the school of the blind, participated in the reconstruction and renovation of Oluwo Palace, sand filling of major roads in the host communities, monetary donations towards community development project among others. It could be deduced from these explanations that Bowen University is a victim of the ignorance of university corporate social responsibility (UCSR); hence her inability to embrace CSR, cultivate its environment and become socially responsible.

This is corroborated by Asemah et al, (2013) that universities are often not seen as organizations that are established for business purpose and so they tend not to embrace CSR. They opined that universities and other tertiary institutions alike need to carry out CSR so as to win the goodwill of their stakeholders. Bowen University in the contrary, allowed the grievances of her host communities to degenerate into unwholesome pestilence which resulted to crisis. This corresponds with the opinions of the Chairmen of the two LGAs that host Bowen University and the University Public Relations Officer. The trio confirmed that the lackadaisical attitude of Bowen University concerning CSR to her host communities during interview which brought about the denial of the goodwill the University by the stakeholders and the resultant effect is crisis.

Considering the effectiveness of the CSR strategies that Bowen University used to resolve the crisis, table 4 shows that 55% of respondents knew about the award of scholarships to students of the host communities by the university while 45% are not aware. 92% of the respondents saw the reconstructed building of the school for the blind at Adeke while 8% had not seen it. 93% of respondents saw the borehole and electrification at Olooya village provided by the university while 7% did not see it. 60% of the respondents knew that Bowen University constructed a culvert at Yidi Oba while 40% did not know. 65% of respondents are aware that the university contributed funds for the reconstruction and renovation of Oluwo Palace while 35% are not aware. 90% saw the sand filling of the host communities' roads by Bowen University while 10% did not see it. 70% of respondents

knew about the employment of indigenes of host communities by the university while 30% did not know about it. 55% of respondents are aware of the award of contracts to indigenes of the host communities by Bowen University while 45% did not know about it. 56% knew about the monetary donations towards community development project of the host communities by the university while 44% did not know about it.

These show that majority of the respondents agree that the CSR strategies used by the Bowen University as a crisis management tool to address the crises with her host communities were effective. Similarly, two of the three interviewees also confirmed that the strategies were effective. According to them, if Bowen University had done all these before now there will be no need for grievances and by extension, no crisis. This is in conformity with the assumption of the stakeholders' theory which stipulates that organization have obligations to the group that make up the environment where it operates and therefore should invest in the society. For example, Abu Karim and Audu (2016) said that the Federal Polytechnic Ida, Kogi state has been committed to various stakeholders through CSR such as admission policy that favours indigenes of the host community, provision of pipe born water, employment opportunities, and award of contracts to the immediate community. Dahan and Snol (2012) in the same vein aver that universities, especially private ones are in need of strong corporate strategies in order to be successful in the highly competitive educational industry. They said that CSR had become one of the highly preferred strategies by higher educational institutions for gaining a good reputation and competitive advantage. It is equally a strategic tool in the ambience of crisis resolution between an organization and its host community.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Universities represent a vital part of any society and therefore should corporatize in order to enjoy the goodwill of the environment where it operates. CSR is not just legal compliance. It is also ethical, philanthropic and economic move to enhance sustainability, productivity and build harmonious co-existence between institution and its host community. It has been observed that before now, universities and other related tertiary institutions do not embrace CSR, Bowen University inclusive. They believe that CSR is meant for only organizations that are established solely for profit making. Today, globalization has embraced tertiary institutions and universities had begun to experience a significant paradigm shift from the old fashioned method of confining itself to classroom waiting for grants or subventions from its proprietors to dynamic, resourceful and result-oriented institutions that are both entrepreneurial and technological driven with sound ethical and social responsibilities. The reason is that host communities and stakeholders no longer allow themselves to be treated anyhow by the organizations that operate in their societies. They have become alive to their legitimate demands and aspirations.

This narrative has changed the environment in which organizations function. Universities and indeed tertiary institutions in Nigeria should adopt these new economic

realities in order to meet the changing dynamics and revolutionary trends that now exist between organizations and her host communities and Bowen University should not be exempted, having experienced crisis which came as a result of its inability to invest in the society where they operates. This study has demonstrated that CSR has become a proactive means to crisis resolution and Bowen University is not in isolation. This study concludes by asserting that CSR is not only a recognizable tool for crisis management but also for promoting mutual understanding and goodwill between an organization and her host community. It recommends that universities, especially private ones should embrace CSR strategies in order to be successful and self-sustaining in the highly competitive educational industry.

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Knowledge and Utilization of ICT among Adult Literacy Facilitators

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Abstract

This study investigated the level of knowledge and utilization of ICTs among adult literacy facilitators in order to identify the inhibiting factors towards the use of ICT by facilitators in South-West Nigeria. It is now obvious that any adult literacy programme that will make lasting impact (functional literacy) should take advantage of ICT. Such understanding is required for designing and implementing appropriate non-formal educational policies and promotes the effective use of ICT by facilitators. A survey design that employed the use of reliability index $r = 0.73$ Cronbach alpha, questionnaire and unstructured interviews was adopted for data collection. Fifty Facilitators selected from six literacy centers in Ondo and Oyo States of South Western Nigeria were sampled using simple random and purposive sampling techniques. All the completed copies of the questionnaire were found usable. The data analysis indicated that respondents had a low usage of ICT. More so, infrastructural facilities like electricity have the greatest inhibiting effect on the utilization of ICT as 70% of the respondents reported that lack of electricity inhibit their utilization of ICT by them. There is a positive, strong and significant relationship between ICT knowledge and ICT utilization among the respondents. The correlation coefficient of 0.843 indicates a positive and strong relationship between knowledge of ICT and utilization of ICT among the respondents. The p value at 0.000 which is less than 0.05 significance level indicates that the relationship between the two variables is significant. Though the mean of the male respondents was higher than their female counterparts in the utilization of ICT, the mean difference is however not significant. There is no significant age difference in the utilization of ICT among the respondents.

Word Counts 276

Key words: Knowledge, CT Utilization, Adult Literacy, Facilitators

Introduction

To a large extent, literacy in the adult education world in the new dispensation is bound to thrive effectively with the incorporation of ICT. Organizers of Adult Literacy Education including Facilitators are expected to avail themselves of the utilitarian values of ICT to bring about total inclusion of the adult learners in different spheres of life. The term ICT refers to the convergence of audio-visual and telephone networks with computer networks through a single cabling or link system. The term stresses the use of computers as well as necessary enterprise software, middleware, storage, and audio-visual systems to access, store, transmit, and manipulate information. (Sahay, 2003).

Information technology is the use of man-made tools for the collection, generation, communication, recording, re-management and exploitation of information (Anyakoha 1991 as cited by Agbolahor, 2005). ICT includes those applications by which information is transferred, recorded, edited, stored, manipulated or disseminated. Information technology is a revolution which has penetrated almost all fields of human activity, thus transforming economic and social life (Hawkridge 1983 as cited by Hedman, & Borell, 2004).

Rapid development of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) has led to significant changes in education, social, economic and political relations of the modern society, access to information and control over it contribute to the prevalence of soft power in politics of digital age (Wong, Sandy, Choi & Lee, 2008). Knowledge of ICT will empower the adult facilitators and adult learners in international relations and in the delivery of their services; there is widespread research interest in Information and Communication Technologies because ICT is crucially important. It can be used in literacy education for functional literacy and sustainable development.

Ogbomo and Ogbomo (2008) noted that for the past two decades most developed countries have witnessed significant changes that can be traced to ICTs. These multi-dimensional changes have been observed in almost all aspects of life: economics, education, communication, health among others. In a technology driven society, getting information quickly is important for both senders and receivers. ICTs have made it possible to quickly find and distribute information.

Many initiatives have been taken at the international level to support Africa's efforts to develop communication infrastructures and these efforts are designed to enable African countries including Nigeria, to find faster ways to achieve durable and sustainable development.

Annan (2002) stated that, ICT has paved way for human capacity to be expanded, built up, nourished, and liberated by giving people access to tools of technology with the education and training to use them effectively. Adult facilitators should be vast in ICT so as to help adult learners become vast in ICT: this is one of the surest ways of ensuring functional literacy.

Over the last couple of years, the African continent has seen major advancements in technology – from both an adoption and manufacturing point of view. The ecommerce wave

has officially hit modern societies, and rather than sinking, the African market is learning to swim, very quickly. Technology companies, much like Realm Digital, have gone on to see great success in the local and international markets, and foreign investors are more keen and comfortable to invest their money in this market segment. While the continent's infrastructure continues to be a challenge in embracing technology, the market is willing to engage with new technology to improve their education, knowledge and skills (Jill, 2016).

For example, in West and Central Africa, Nigeria leads the way in usage of ICT with 63 million internet users, ranking 9th in the world. Most of the access is through mobile devices. Cloud computing is being hailed as an 'African success story'. The continents' leaders believe that cloud technology has the potential to transform the technology industry and even daily activities. In Nigeria, pharmacists and patients are using a cloud-based service to verify the authenticity of prescription medicines, while in Kenya, local innovators created a cloud-based market-tracking app for farmers trying to get the best prices for their goods. Rwanda recently launched Africa's first drone delivery programme. In partnership with a Californian-based startup, 50 to 150 daily deliveries of critical medical supplies to 21 locations across Rwanda. Rwanda has a clear development strategy in place, with ICT at the heart of its transformation. Thus, with consistent effort, Africa can become a vital part of the world digital transformation (Jill, 2016). One of the identified agents through which the world will constantly experience change in technology in the business of trying to make information available in the right form to the right users at the right time both at the personal and organizational levels is ICT: the bid to cope with great flood of information has led to the need for a more sophisticated way of handling information faster and better (Karahanna, Agarwal, & Angst, 2006).

UNDP (2001) asserts that even if sustainable economic growth facilitates the creation and diffusion of useful innovations, technology is not only the result of growth but can be used to support growth and development. ICTs are credited with the ability to transform and cause significant changes in handling all aspects of life better. Thus, its use for facilitation in literacy classes should be encouraged: facilitators should take maximum advantage of technologies and adapt ICTs to local conditions for instructions in literacy classes, and help learners understand those innovations and adjust them to their own development. In June 1996, the United Nations Commission on Science and Technology Development (UNCSTD) proposed five development indicators that focused on the improvement of the quality of life: education, health, income, governance, and technology (Crede & Mansell, 1998; Ogbomo &

Ogbomo, 2008). ICTs can be socially beneficial because it contributes to poverty eradication (higher income), improved health and education, better use and more equitable sharing of resources, and raising participation in the decision-making processes. In this regard, access to information and communication technology is crucial. ICTs have been the basis for human existence from time immemorial and this has driven man to continuously seek ways to improve the processing of information and communicating such information to one another irrespective of distance and on a real-time basis (Mary & David, 2006). Surviving in the information age depends on access to national and global information networks. ICTs are the bedrock for the survival and development of any nation in a rapidly changing global environment, and it challenges us to devise initiatives to address a host of issues such as reliable infrastructure, skilled human resources, open government, and other essential issues of capacity building, the two branches of ICT include computing and telecommunication. The technologies covered are the computer system, Internet/electronic mail (e-mail), mobile phone, and fax machine. ICTs offer real opportunities to improve the quality of community life. It is also important to deepen our level of reflection on community dynamics and on the constraints encountered when introducing and using ICTs for development, a healthy information society is concerned with getting reliable and timely information to its members. Making people aware of the benefits derivable from the use of ICTs will help to make the society a healthy one (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2001).

On the other hand, Adult Education refers to the set of educational activities made available to adults persons in a given society to ensure inclusion and fulfillment of adult persons socially, economically and intellectually (Odiaka, 2018). According to Odiaka this form of education remain the only forms of education that can fill the gaps left by formal schooling in Nigeria. This function of adult education is possible because of the following features that differentiate it from primary or secondary school education:

- It can be formal informal or non-formal.

- It recognizes the wealth of experiences possessed by adult learners.

- It is diversify to cope with varying needs of adult learners.

- It encapsulates distance learning; continue education, including extra moral learning.

According to Godwin (2013), adult education is the process to provide education to the adults and aged people who, somehow had failed to receive the elementary education during their childhood. Goswani (2013) noted that adults are independents, self-directed goal oriented and are always relating learning to immediate problems. These assertions imply that different categories of adult learners abound since they have different entry behaviours, disposition and cultures.

The onus lies on the facilitators to desire means by which there clientele can be adequately taught to ensure the realization of the objectives of adult learning in Nigeria. Since literacy is at the heart of adult learning and ICT being a significant part of literacy, it is given gaining ample attention as the in the field of adult education. It is both a tool for instruction for the facilitators and a content area of learning the knowledge of ICT including acquiring skills on the use of OC, manipulating the Icons, and using them purposefully. Utilising ICT

includes using different ICT gadgets for storing, processing and retrieving information. It entails using emails and social networks to achieve various academic and social problems.

Other nature of adult education which feature distance learning, diversified content and heterogeneous demands that facilitators require the use of ICT for facilitating adult learning. NMEC and ANFE (Agency for Adult and Non-Formal Education) as highly organised bodies that cater for adult education activities in the entire country have been doing much in training and provision of learning materials. However, there is need to carry out an empirical study to examine the extent to which facilitators have acquired knowledge and skills of ICT.

Figure 1: ICT Literacy Model
Adapted from O'Connor (2002:18)

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed that majority of the neo-literate (graduates of adult basic literacy classes) still seek help regarding how they are to use their personal computer, they cannot open or shut down their computer systems properly, storing and retrieving information from their systems and phones, opening and checking their E-mails, applying for jobs online, sourcing for related write-ups using search engines such as Google to do their assignments have remained hardened tasks. Some of them cannot even search and dial up numbers on their cell phones without help, yet they are certified literate.

The reason is not far-fetched: they were not taught, probably because their tutors were not ICT skilled. Considering the fact that employers expect prospective employees to be ICT-literate. How can these set of neo-literate easily secure jobs? Thus, it is expected that adults should be taught and encouraged to take advantage of ICT in order to continue to cope in this contemporary world. Adult literacy facilitators should be vast in ICT so as to help adult learners become vast in ICT, they should take advantage of audio-visuals such as audiobooks, audiocassettes and audio CDs, bulletin board kits, CD ROMs and Charts, DVDs, games and maps, models, puppets and picture sets, posters, transparencies, and videocassettes as instructional materials to aid teaching-learning process when exchanging knowledge with adult learners. They cannot continue to stick only to the traditional materials and style of

literacy teaching.... how can facilitators without ICT knowledge help adult learners in ICT related issues?

Thus: there is need to access the knowledge and utilization of information communication technology (ICT) among adult literacy facilitators and if need be, train the facilitators who will in-turn train and educate the adult learners to be aware of ICT, to embrace it, willing to use it. Most studies on ICT use focused on determining organizational level use and factors that promote or hinder ICT use at that level. Some of these studies have postulated that under-utilization of IT in Nigeria is due to factors such as poor funding of ICT, high cost of IT equipment among others. Little researches have been done in assessing whether facilitators have the basic knowledge of ICT required and on the importance of ICT teaching in basic adult literacy curriculum. Therefore, this study examines the knowledge and utilization of ICT among adult facilitators in South-West Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of knowledge, utilization and importance of ICT among adult literacy facilitators in south-west Nigeria?
2. What are the perceived factors inhibiting ICT utilization among adult literacy facilitators of south-west Nigeria?
3. Is there any relationship between ICT knowledge and ICT utilization among adult literacy facilitators of south-west Nigeria?
4. Is there relationship between age and utilization of ICT among adult literacy facilitators of south-west Nigeria?
5. Is there any significant relationship between gender and utilization of ICT among adult literacy facilitators of south-west Nigeria?

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design of the ex post facto type. The Population comprised the adult facilitators in south-western Nigeria. The simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were used to select respondents adult literacy facilitators from Odogbo Barracks Literacy Centre Ojoo, Ibadan and Moniya Garage literacy, Centre Moniya in Akinyele Local Government Area (LGA), Immanuel College Literacy Centre, Orita UI, Ibadan and Wumani-Alaga Literacy Centre, Sango, Ibadan North, LGA of Oyo State. AUD Primary school Literacy Centre Ipele, Government Primary School Literacy Centre, Owo and Mapo Hall Literacy , Owo in Owo LGA area of Ondo State.

A total of 50 adult facilitators (respondents) were drawn from two States (Oyo and Ondo) for the study. The study utilized a self-structured questionnaire tagged Questionnaire on Knowledge of ICT among Adult Literacy Facilitators (QKICTALF) and Questionnaire on utilization of ICT among Adult Literacy Facilitators (QUICTALF). Cronbach Alpha reliability values yielded are; QKICTALF ($r=0.81$) QUICTALF ($r=0.84$); while both QKICTALF and QUICTALF yielded $r= 0.73$) Cronbach alpha. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency count, simple percentage, and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient.

Result and Discussions

Research Question One: What is the level of knowledge, utilization and relevance of ICT among adult literacy facilitators in south-west Nigeria?

Table1. Frequency counts and simple percentages showing Facilitators’ knowledge, utilization and importance of ICTs

S/N	Items	Agree		Disagree	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1.	ICT includes knowledge of unified communications and the integration of telecommunications	46	92	4	8
2.	ICT includes knowledge of internet tools and computer applications	46	92	4	8
3.	ICT includes knowledge of software and hardware	44	88	6	12
4.	ICT enables users to have access to and manipulate information	44	88	6	12
5.	I have already acquired the knowledge of ICT	12	24	38	76
6.	I know how to apply these skills to helping my adult learners	21	42	29	58
7.	I know how to apply ICT skills to aid my personal learning	15	30	35	70
8.	I know how to switch on computer system	42	84	8	16
9.	I know how to store information on computer	13	26	37	74
10.	I know how to retrieve information stored on the computer	12	24	38	76
11.	I know how to shut down computer system	38	76	12	24
12.	I know that people including facilitators without ICT knowledge cannot make global impact	13	26	37	74
13.	I know how to use e-mails to send and receive information	10	20	40	80
14.	I know how to use social networks	10	20	10	20
15.	I know that ICT knowledge is crucial in the realization of literacy goals and objectives	5	10	45	90
16.	I know that knowledge of ICT can help stimulate a learner’s interest	3	6	47	94
17.	Primer, real literacy materials, local newspapers, etc. without knowledge of ICT is not enough to help students become literate in this contemporary world	5	10	45	90
18.	I know that adult learners should be encouraged to learn in details as such aspect of ICT related to their individual activities	2	4	48	96

The findings of the study as shown in the table above indicate that respondents have a fairly high level of awareness but low knowledge of ICT skills. The percentage responses to the items seeking information on knowledge of ICT reveal that the level of knowledge of ICT among the respondents is considerably high. Percentage responses on items 1-4 which sought general information on recognition of ICT constituents indicate that respondents have good knowledge of ICT constituents as the items recorded percentage responses of 92%, 92%, 88% and 88% respectively for items 1-4.

On the utilization of ICT, findings reveal that respondents reported a low level of usage of ICT equipment. Unfortunately, however, 58% of these respondents stated that they do not know how to apply ICT knowledge and skills in facilitating the learning of their adult students. It was also found that 70% of the respondents reported that they cannot apply ICT knowledge and skills for their own learning. It is regrettable that in this information age, 16% and 24% of the respondents respectively reported that they cannot switch on or shut down the computer. In a similar vein, finding revealed that 76% of the respondents reported that they cannot store information on the computer with the same percentage reporting that they cannot retrieve stored information on the computer. Findings also indicate that 80% of the respondents reported that they cannot utilize the electronic mail in sending and receiving information with another 80% reporting lack of knowledge of how to use social networks.

On the place of ICT in advancing learning, the study found that respondents were unanimous in their assertion that knowledge of ICT is crucial to making global impact with 76% affirming to item 12 which sought information on that. The strongest consensus was however on the place of ICT in advancing educational goals and objectives as well as in advancing adult learners interest in learning. Items 15-18 which sought information on these areas have percentage responses of 90%, 94%, 90% and 96% respectively.

Research Question Two What are the perceived factors inhibiting ICT utilization among adult literacy facilitators of south-west Nigeria?

Table 2: Factors Inhibiting Utilization of ICT among Respondents

Inhibiting Factors	Yes		No	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Availability	50	50	50	50
Accessibility	22	44	28	56
Infrastructural facilities e.g. electricity	35	70	15	30
Lack of knowledge of use	16	32	34	68

The findings of the study as shown in the table reveals that infrastructural facilities like electricity have the greatest inhibitory effect on the utilization of ICT as 70% of the respondents reported that lack of electricity inhibit their utilization of ICT by them. Another worrisome percentage (50%) reported that they do not use ICT because the facilities and equipment are not available while 44% reported that even when these ICT facilities are available, they are not accessible. This lack of accessibility might not be unconnected with poor working state and condition of these facilities which is the general situation in government agencies and establishments where little consideration is placed on maintenance. Findings also revealed that 32% of the respondents revealed that they do not use ICT because they do not have knowledge of its usage. The percentage might be considered small but it is actually worrisome that in this jet age such a percentage can be reported to be lacking good knowledge on ICT use.

Research Question Three: What is the relationship between ICT knowledge and ICT utilization among adult literacy facilitators in south-west Nigeria?

Table 3: Correlation Table Showing Relationship between Knowledge and Utilization of ICT

		Knowledge	Utilization
Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	.843**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	50	50
Utilization	Pearson Correlation	.843**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	50	50

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The finding of the study as shown in the correlation table above reveals that there is a positive, strong and significant relationship between ICT knowledge and ICT utilization among the respondents. The correlation coefficient at 0.843 indicates a positive and strong relationship between knowledge of ICT and utilization of ICT among the respondents. The p value at 0.000 which is less than 0.05 significance level indicates that the relationship between the two variables is significant. The implication of this is that with increased level of knowledge on ICT there is corresponding increase in the utilization of ICT. The r^2 value at 0.711 reveals that 71.1% of the variance in utilization of ICT among the respondents was accounted for by knowledge of ICT thus revealing the large extent to which knowledge of ICT is related to its utilization. Any effort aimed at increasing the utilization of ICT among the respondents must be grounded in increasing the level of knowledge of ICT use among the

respondents as the study has revealed that with increased knowledge, there will be increased utilization.

Research Question Four: Will there be significant gender difference in the utilization of ICT among adult literacy facilitators in south-west Nigeria?

Table 4: T-Test Table Mean difference of ICT Utilization by Gender

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t _{obt.}	df	t _{crit.}	P
Utilization	Male	31	49.55	11.168	1.223	48	2.00	.227
	Female	19	45.63	10.699				

The finding of the study as indicated in the t-test table above reveals that though the mean of the male respondents was higher than their female counterparts in the utilization of ICT, the mean difference is however not significant. The male respondents recorded a mean value of 49.55 while the female respondents recorded a mean of 45.63. The p value at 0.227 which is greater than 0.05 reveals that the mean difference by gender is not significant. This is further corroborated by the value of t obtained which is less than the value of t table at degree of freedom of 48 thus showing that though there is mean difference by gender, the difference is however not significant. As such, it is concluded that though there is mean difference by gender in the utilization of ICT among the respondents, the difference is not significant. This finding is in line with the assertion of Sarumi 2011, when he asserted that, a lot of empowerment programmes have now been put in place... women are now being made aware of the opportunities around, they are also encouraged especially by UNESCO to be assertive, educated, and acquire relevant skills in all ramifications with the strong belief that, without women's participation in decision-making in all spheres of life poverty will not be eradicated, nor will fully democratic societies be created. These initiatives have helped a great deal to promoting gender equality in the field of ICT competences.

Research Question Five: Will there be significant age difference in the utilization of ICT among adult literacy facilitators in south-west Nigeria?

Table 5: ANOVA Table Showing Age Effect on Utilization of ICT among Respondents

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	78.560	2	39.280	.313	.733
Within Groups	5904.260	47	125.623		
Total	5982.820	49			

The finding of the study as shown in the ANOVA table above reveals that there is no significant age difference in the utilization of ICT among the respondents. With an F value of 0.313 which is less than F table value at df of 2,47 which is 3.19 indicates that there is no significant mean difference by age among the respondents in ICT utilization. This is further affirmed by the p value which is greater than 0.05 at 0.733. This finding is in line the submission of UNESCO 2011 which says age is not really a factor in ICT related issues but degree of individual exposure and years of experience in ICT related issues. And it must be noted that the individuals can only be vast in areas of ICT been exposed to, therefore, someone may be literate in one or more aspect of ICT but illiterate in other areas of ICT.

Summary of Findings

The findings of the study as shown in the table above indicate that respondents have a fairly high level of awareness but low knowledge of ICT skills. On the utilization of ICT, findings reveal that respondents reported a low level of usage of ICT equipment. On the place of ICT in advancing learning, the study found that respondents were unanimous in their assertion that knowledge of ICT is crucial to making meaningful educational impacts.

Findings of the study shows that infrastructural facilities like electricity have the greatest inhibitory effect on the utilization of ICT others include non-availability of ICTs equipment in the Literacy centers, non-accessibility of ICTs equipment to the facilitators, and poor working state and condition of these facilities in the few places where they are available which is the general situation in government agencies and establishments where little consideration is placed on maintenance. Lack of ICTs knowledge also inhibits its usage among the facilitators.

Finding also shows that there is a positive, strong and significant relationship between ICT knowledge and ICT utilization among the respondents, with increased level of knowledge on ICT there is corresponding increase in the utilization of ICT. Thus any effort aimed at increasing the utilization of ICT among the Facilitators should be grounded in increasing the level of knowledge of ICT among the respondents.

Finding also shows that though the mean of the male respondents was higher than their female counterparts in the utilization of ICT, the mean difference is however not significant.

Finding of the study further shows that there is no significant age difference in the utilization of ICT among the facilitators; this result is true because large proportion of the adult basic literacy facilitators in this study reported that, they were retired teachers from the

Formal education sector. They are all old with no significant age differences in their usage of ICTs. And it should be noted that the individuals can only be vast in areas of ICT been exposed to, therefore, someone may be literate in one or more aspect of ICT but illiterate in other areas of ICT.

Conclusion

This study has provided empirical data about the knowledge, gender, It has also established relationship between age of facilitators and ICT utilization as well as gender and ICT utilization among facilitators: It can be concluded from the study that although there is a large proportion of facilitators in the south western Nigeria, findings revealed that only 20% of the respondents reported that they use computer to teach their lessons. In fact, the low level of utilization of ICT in instruction among the facilitators was also shown in the percentage responses on item 10 which sought information on the utilization of power point presentations for teaching. Findings revealed that only 18% of the respondents reported using power point presentations for instructional purposes. Notwithstanding that, 80% of the respondents affirmed that ICT utilization enhances facilitators' activities as revealed by percentage responses on item 13 only 20% and 18% actually use computer to teach and power point presentations respectively in literacy classes. Therefore, there is need for adult literacy organizers to emphasize maximum usage of ICT in literacy classes by ensuring continuous training and encourage the tutors to take full advantage of ICT.

Recommendations

The non-governmental organizations such as UNESCO, UNIVA, UNDP, IFESH, UNICEF, the World Bank should not relent in their effort in ensuring functional literacy for all. They should continue to fund the non-formal educational sector with special attention to ICT literacy because neo literates who are properly expose to ICT will not easily revert to illiteracy as reviled by the findings of this research.

Findings of The study reveals that lack of infrastructural facilities inhibit ICT use among facilitators. The organizers of Adult literacy programmes should look out for more sources of fund generation other than the government and the NGOs, they should involve the rich individuals, social groups and clubs, religious bodies e.t.c. in the society to fund literacy programmes especially in the provision of ICT facilities.

The facilitators themselves should continue to seek and acquire knowledge and skills of ICT through all available means because the knowledge of ICT is not limited to classroom usage; they need it in all aspects of their lives, every day, every time and everywhere.

Adult Facilitators are hereby informed that employers of labours all around the world has made ICT knowledge and skills with evidence (certificate) one of the major requirements

for job applications, they should therefore, consciously encourage the adult learners to go the extra miles in learning to detail those aspects of ICT related to their day to day activities or dream job.

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**Sanitary Pads Advertising Messages and Buying Behaviour of Female Students of
Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State**

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Abstract

Sanitary pads are of great importance to menstruating women across the globe. The Nigerian sanitary pad market has over twelve brands competing for market shares through advertisement messages to influence the buying behaviour of women folks especially young ladies. This research examined sanitary pad advertising messages and the buying behaviour of female students of Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design, using a researcher-designed questionnaire for data gathering from 300 respondents. Data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that, new media (82%) and broadcast media (72%) are prominent channels through which Adeleke University female students' access sanitary pad advertising messages. Again, to a very large extent, respondents pay attention to contents of sanitary pad advertising messages which motivate them to prefer the absorbent quality, skin friendly features and stain preventive functions of sanitary pads. Therefore, buying behaviour of the respondents is hinged on the benefits of the products contained in the advertisement messages. The study recommends that advertisers and advertising agencies should emphasize the benefits of products in advertising messages. The study also recommended that advertising messages should be creatively tailored towards the information needs of consumers. Also, Manufacturers of sanitary pads should ensure quality service delivery.

Keywords: Advertising, Advertising Messages, Buying Behaviour, Consumers,

Sanitary Pads

Word Count: 205

Introduction

Advertising, just like selling is not a new phenomenon. People can only speculate when the first advertisements were created. Early advertisements can be traced to Ancient Egypt, Ancient Rome, and Ancient Greek where promoting words were carved on stones by the roadside, gladiator shows were advertised on the wall and town criers shouted advertisements in the streets respectively. These formed the basic principles of modern advertising as it is practiced today (Rodman, 2012). Again advertising is a form of communication in the mass media about products, services or ideas paid for by identifiable sponsors. Advertising communicates information about specific products, services and ideas to target audiences. Advertising is a means to inform consumers about the existence of products educate them on the importance and significance of the products and persuade them to buy and consume such products, services or idea. Basically, advertising serves the purpose of the advertiser or the identifiable sponsor. Advertising is a specific kind of communication effort that is based on purchasing time or space in the communication media in order to send the message concerning a product, service or idea, with the aim of eliciting favorable response (Ihebuzor and Akpobo, 2020).

Advertisement is usually not directed at one person but a substantial number of individuals or groups that may number up to millions of people. This statement summarises the importance of an advertising message and its influence over target audiences. Advertising conveys persuasive, informative and educative messages intended to sell the advertiser's products to the target audience. These messages are called advertising messages. Advertising messages are the information professionally prepared by copywriters and disseminated through advertising media to sell products, services or ideas. These messages are tailored towards directing the attention of a target audience to a product and generating purchases.

Advertisers use advertising to attract favourable consumer behavior towards their products, services or idea. Consumer buying behaviour is an important variable in this study. Consumer buying behavior has evolved over the years. It is a special concept with the distinctive means to access knowledge about consumers, which is a measurable source of progress. Consumer buying behaviour is attracting the interest of different researchers from different disciplines (Makarewicz, 2013). Consumer buying behaviour is a

psychological process in an individual that influences their purchasing behaviour towards any goods services and idea (Barmola & Srivastava, 2010). Sanitary pad is important for healthy reproductive health and general wellbeing. Reproductive health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease in all matters relating to the functioning and processes of the reproductive system (WHO, 2021).

Reproductive health infers that individuals are able to have a healthy and safe sex life that ensures the capability to reproduce as they see fit (WHO, 2021). Human rights regarding sexuality and reproduction are important in order to enable individuals, particularly women and girls, have active roles in their own health safety, education and to fully participate in social and economic life (Medicins du Monde, 2021). Sexual and reproductive health are basic human rights that are vital for human development. Different countries have adopted international development programme till 2030. Sexual and reproductive health must be emphasized as the cornerstone of sustainable development (Medicins du Monde, 2021).

Advertising message or the message of an advertisement is the substance of the advertisement. It conveys the intentions of the advertiser through words audio, visual and graphic element. It is the thought, idea, image, or any other information that the advertiser wishes to let the target audience know (Alok, 2021). The way advertising message is presented is important for its effectiveness. The creative team should not only put in effort into the content of the message, but also on delivery, feedback and appeal (Alok, 2021). Advertisement message is simply the intention of the advertisers crafted with words, images or audio visual components.

The author's assertion of advertising reveals the 5Ws and H of advertising, which are;

1. **What:** Communication
2. **Who:** Identifiable Sponsor (Advertiser)
3. **Where:** Media
4. **Why:** To promote products, services and idea
5. **How:** This requires the collaborative effort of Advertising Messages, Advertising Agency or Specialists, Media and Advertisers

Advertising message content, media planning and repetitive campaigns constitute a big part of a strategy that triggers the reaction mechanisms of the target market. Reaction

mechanisms can be psychological components of an individual, such as cognitive or emotional reactions, that reflects in expressed behaviour: acquisition loyalty, among many others (Nichifor, 2014). Today, advertising is an important aspect of everyday life. It influences mental perception of life and attitudes of people in the world. It is used to construct what is good and what is bad as desired by the advertiser (Svetlana, 2014).

Advertising message is an idea an advertiser wants to communicate to its target audience. Advertising campaigns are usually directed towards conveying an advertising message to a target market in order to induce purchase of a product or service and promote brand awareness (Cavallari, 2021). This is done through different methods, each enhancing consumer recall of products and ability to identify it with quality and desire. Advertising messages is delivered through different media, such as television, radio, print, word of mouth, events, and so on (Cavallari, 2021).

The components of advertising message are: the tagline, the slogan, the appeal, and the value. Each component of the advertising message has a role in persuading the target market to purchase products or services. The tagline is a statement, image, video, or other type of media that attracts the audience's attention and makes them find out more about the particular advertisement (Office on Women Health, 2021). This tagline needs to be unique to stand out from all other things that can keep the audience from noticing the products, services or idea (Cavallari, 2021).

Indicators for effective advertising according to Dahl (2007) include:

- A. **Creative:** Effective advertising presents the advertising message in an innovative, distinctive way.
- B. **Attention Grabbing:** Its headline, copy, or graphic element should attract the attention of the target market.
- C. **Memorable:** It should conduct in a way that the audience can easily recall and associate with the brand.
- D. **Clear:** It presents its message in a concise, simple, easily understood manner.
- E. **Informative:** It enlightens the audience about the advertisers business and products, while providing them with reasons to patronize the brand.
- F. **Distinctive:** It is unique and easily identifiable.

Advertising message is a process. It is the result or end product of a creative process that involves imagination, ideation, conceptualization and actualization towards

communicating with target audience with the mission of promoting the advertiser's product, services and ideas. Advertising messages can be text, audio, visual messages and Word of Mouth. Advertising message is a system. It is the means by which elements such as language, audio, graphics are refined to form a comprehensive logical message disseminated through the media to get the desired response of the advertiser from then consumers or target market.

Consumer buying behaviour entails the study of individuals and the method they adopt to select, use, and set out products, services and idea to satisfy their wants and the consequences that these methods have on consumers and society (Khaniwale, 2015). It is the combination of thoughts, feelings and actions that influences an individual pre-purchase, purchase and post-purchase decisions. Buyer behaviour is a framework which provide rational explanation as to what, why, how, when and where a customer makes purchase, the end result of which is the buyer's decision (Khaniwale, 2015).

Consumer buying behaviour refers to the process of choosing, purchasing and consuming goods and services to satisfy consumer needs and wants (Ramya and Mohammed, 2016). Consumer buying behaviour is a discipline of study that explores the buying tendencies of consumers (Indirani, 2015). This is done to provide a rational explanation to the unpredictable attitude of consumers when it concerns buying. A person who goes to the market does not necessarily buy products. There are stages a customer goes through before purchase (Indirani, 2015).

Sanitary pads were first made commercially available in the market were in 1888, in 2021 however, it is an important female hygiene product. In the report titled "Sanitary Napkin Market: Global Industry Trends, Share, Size, Growth, Opportunity and Forecast 2018-2023", the global sanitary napkin market was stated to have reach a value of US\$ 19.5 Billion in 2017 (Moore 2021). There are a number of factors that have made sanitary napkins one of the most popular option for menstrual management. Economic development and encouraging market conditions are two factors that encourage affordability sanitary (Moore 2021).

In 2018, the value of the global sanitary napkins market was estimated to be 20.5 billion U.S. dollars and was forecast to reach to roughly 28 billion dollars by 2022 (Shewan, 2017). Sanitary pads are menstrual products worn by women, basically to absorb menstrual blood. It is a widely used product that consists of layers of quilted cotton

fabrics and alternative layers of super absorbent polymers, plastics, fragrance and antibacterial agents (Research and Market, 2021).

The study was based on Information Processing Theory: Information processing theory was conceived by American psychologists including George Miller, in the 1950s. It is a cognitive theory that focuses on how information is encoded into human memory. It describes how the human brains filter information from what they pay attention to in the present moment to what get stored in human short term or working memory and ultimately into long term memory (Hatague & Nabua, 2017). In 1956, George Miller was among the first to apply a step-by-step theory to information processing by relating it to the way that high-speed computers processed information. He proposed that, similar to a computer, the human mind takes information, performs operations on it to change its form and content, stores and locates the information, and then generates output of some type (Rosnov & Roberts, 2015). The theory was formally propounded by Williams McGuire in 1968.

There are six steps involved in the process by which an advertisement message cause change in attitude of the receiver (Anaeto, Onabajo & Osifeso, 2012). They include:

- i. A persuasive advertisement message should be transmitted.
- ii. The recipient should attend to messages transmitted.
- iii. The recipient should comprehend the message
- iv. The encoder yields to and is influenced by the promises presented.
- v. The newly acquired position is retained.
- vi. The required behaviour takes place.

This means that an advertisement when transmitted should attract the attention of consumers. Consumers should come in contact with brand advertisement (Awareness) and understand the message conveyed through advertising in order form perception about the brand. The advertisement message attracts the interest the consumer and influences the decision to buy or not buy a particular brand of sanitary pad.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian sanitary pad market is rapidly growing and highly competitive and the buying behaviour of Nigerian women towards sanitary pads is an important causative factor. The availability of variety of brands creates the need to know what influences Nigerian women to buy particular brands of pad. Such brands include: *Always, Molped, Virony, Angel*

Secret, Diva Kotex, Longrich and Lady Care, among many others. Different manufacturers advertise their brands of sanitary pad on different media. Despite this, there is no significant information that explains why Nigerian women buy particular brands of sanitary pads. Literatures is scanty on the relationship between sanitary pad advertising messages and the buying behaviour of Nigeria women. The study therefore examines the relationship between sanitary pads advertisement messages and the buying behaviour of female students of Adeleke University.

Objectives of the Study

This study examines the relationship between sanitary pads advertising messages and the buying behaviour of female students of Adeleke University. Other specific objectives of the study are to:

1. identify the channels through which female students of Adeleke University access sanitary pad advertising messages
2. ascertain the extent to which Adeleke University female students pay attention to sanitary pad advertisement messages
3. examine the extent to which advertising messages motivate brand patronage of sanitary pads by female students in Adeleke University
4. determine the brands of sanitary pad regularly purchased by female students of Adeleke University.
5. examine the reasons female students of Adeleke University buy certain brands of pad.

Research Questions

The main research question is what is the influence of sanitary pads advertising messages on the buying behaviour of female students of Adeleke University using sanitary pads?

Other questions are:

1. What are the channels through which the female students of Adeleke University access advertising messages about sanitary pads?
2. To what extent do Adeleke University female students pay attention to sanitary pad advertisement messages?

3. To what extent do advertising messages motivate brand patronage of sanitary pads among female students of Adeleke University?
4. What brands of sanitary pad do female students of Adeleke University purchase?
5. Why do female students of Adeleke University buy their choice brands of sanitary pad?

Methodology

The study was a quantitative study. The research design for the study was the descriptive survey research design. The population of this study comprised all female students in the six faculties in Adeleke University, Ede: Faculty of Law, Faculty of Business and Social Sciences, Faculty of Science, Faculty of Arts, Faculty of Engineering and Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences. According to Adeleke University Student Registry, the total number of female students in the university is 1,068. Information from the Adeleke University Registry states that female students are 1,068 in number. Using multi-stage sampling technique; the sample size 300 students was randomly selected from the total number of female undergraduates of Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria. Majority of the respondents 168 (56.0%) are young adults within the age range of 21-30. The research instrument used for data collection was questionnaire with close ended questions; copies of questionnaires were administered to respondents through their respective departmental and faculty forums. The data collected was analysed using simple percentages, tables and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Results and Discussion

Research Question One: What are the channels through which female students of Adeleke University access advertising messages about sanitary pads?

Table 1: Respondents Channel of Access to Sanitary Pads Advertising Messages

Items	AI	OFT	SMT	RLY	NVR	M
	%	%	%	%	%	
I access sanitary pad advertisement messages through broadcast media as radio and television	120 (40%)	60 (20%)	36 (12%)	30 (10%)	54 (18%)	3.54
I access sanitary pad advertisement messages through print media	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	300 (100%)	1
I access sanitary pad advertisement messages through new media as social media, blogs and websites	150 (50%)	60 (20%)	36 (12%)	42 (14%)	12 (4%)	3.98
I access sanitary pad advertisement messages through outdoor media Billboards, Display Bus or Van	2 (0.7%)	1 (0.3%)	1 (0.3%)	5 (1.7%)	291 (97%)	1.06

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Key: 5-Always, 4-Often, 3-Sometimes, 2-Rarely and 1- Never

Table 1 reveals the channels through which Female students of Adeleke University access advertising messages about sanitary pad. Majority of the 246 (82%) respondent's access sanitary pad advertisement messages from new media such as social media, blogs and websites among many others. A second majority of respondents 216 (72%) respondents access advertisement messages from broadcast media such as radio and television. Only 4 (1.3%) of the respondents access sanitary pad advertisement messages through outdoor media such as Billboards, Display Bus or Van. None of the respondents access sanitary pad advertisement messages through print media. In summary, new media and broadcast media are respective prominent channel through which Adeleke University female students' access sanitary pad advertising messages.

Research Question Two: Extent to which Adeleke University Female Student pay attention to sanitary pad advertisement messages?

Table 2: Attention and Interest Stimulated by Advertising Messages of Sanitary pads

Attention and Interest stimulated by advertising messages	AI %	OF T %	SM T %	RLY %	NVR %	M
I pay attention to sanitary pad advertisement messages	120 (40%)	36 (12%)	108 (36%)	36 (12%)	0 (0%)	3.8
I listen to songs of Sanitary pad advertisement messages	36 (12%)	72 (24%)	96 (32%)	96 (32%)	0 (0%)	3.16
I look out for sanitary pad advertisement messages that explore menstrual hygiene education	108 (36%)	24 (8%)	48 (16%)	84 (28%)	36 (12%)	3.28
I like sanitary pad advertisement messages that realistically portray menstrual experiences	168 (56%)	48 (16%)	60 (20%)	24 (8%)	0 (0%)	4.2
I pay attention to Sanitary pad advertisement messages that are feminist inclined	48 (16%)	60 (20%)	120 (40%)	36 (12%)	36 (12%)	3.16

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Key: 5-Always, 4-Often, 3-Sometimes, 2-Rarely and 1- Never

Table 2 shows that 254 (88%) respondents pay attention to sanitary pad advertisement message as they indicated to doing so “always, often and sometimes” while only 36 (12%) respondents indicated to doing so rarely. 204 (68%) respondents like songs of sanitary pad advertisement messages while 96 (32%) rarely find songs in sanitary pad advertisement appealing. 180 (60%) students like sanitary pad advertisement that explore menstrual hygiene education while 120 (40%) respondents do not. 276 (92%) like sanitary pads that realistically portray menstrual experiences while 24 (8%) rarely do. 228 (76%) of respondents like sanitary pad advertisement messages that are feminist inclined while 72 (24%) do not. In summary this table reveals that Adeleke University female students to a very large extent pay attention to sanitary pad advertisement messages.

Research Question Three: To what extent do advertising messages motivate brand patronage of sanitary pad among female students in Adeleke University?

Table 3: Desire and Action Stimulated by Advertising Messages of Sanitary pads

Buying preferences of sanitary pads	AI (%)	OFT (%)	SMT (%)	RLY (%)	NVR (%)	M
I prefer a particular brand of sanitary pad because the advertisement says it offers protective wings.	48 (16%)	48 (16%)	72 (24%)	84 (28%)	48 (16%)	2.88
I prefer a particular brand of sanitary pad because the advertisement says it comes with pant liners.	66 (22%)	36 (12%)	84 (28%)	72 (24%)	42 (14%)	3.04
I buy a particular brand of sanitary because I like the advertisement message.	120 (40%)	84 (28%)	12 (4%)	60 (20%)	24 (8%)	3.72
I buy a particular brand of sanitary pad because of the brand promise of no leakage in the advertisement.	72 (24%)	60 (20%)	96 (32%)	24 (8%)	48 (16%)	3.28
I buy a particular brand of sanitary pad because of the brand promise of “no skin irritation” in the advertisement	96 (32%)	48 (16%)	120 (40%)	24 (8%)	12 (4%)	3.64

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Key: 5-Always, 4-Often, 3-Sometimes, 2-Rarely and 1- Never

The third research question was “extent to which advertising messages motivate brand patronage of sanitary pad among female students in Adeleke University?” Table 3 revealed that 168 (56%) respondents prefer a particular brand of sanitary pad because the advertisement says it offers protective wings while 132 (44%) do not. 186 (62%) respondents prefer a particular brand of sanitary pad because the advertisement says it comes with pant liners while 114 (38%) respondents indicated to doing so rarely and never. 216 (72%) respondents particularly buy a particular brand of sanitary pad because they like the advertisement message while 84 (28%) do not really do so. 228(42%) respondents buy brand of sanitary pad because of the brand promise of no leakage made in the advertisements. 264 (88%) respondents buy a particular brand of sanitary pad because of the brand promise of no skin irritation.

In summary, this table reveals that advertising messages to a large extent motivate brand patronage. This is however hinged on distinctive qualities and benefits such as; no leakage, no skin irritation and offers functional incentives such as pant liner and protective wings as contained in advertisement messages.

Research Question Four: What brands of sanitary pad do female students in Adeleke University purchase?

Table 4: Respondents Brands of Sanitary Pads

Brands of Sanitary Pads Respondents Buy	Frequency	Percentage
Always	96	32%
Diva	0	0%
Comfit	0	0%
Kotex	0	0%
Dry Love	0	0%
Stayfree	0	0%
Sofy	0	0%
Queen Lady	0	0%
Angel	12	4%
Lady Care	40	13%
Virony	96	32%
Molped	56	19%
Total	300	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 4 reveals that 96 (32%) respondents buy Always Sanitary pad, another group of 96 (32%) respondents buy *Virony* Sanitary pad, 56 (19%) respondents buy *Molped* sanitary pad, 40 (13%) respondents buy *Lady Care* and 12 (4%) respondents buy Angel Secret.

Popular brands of sanitary pad among female students of Adeleke University are; *Always*, *Virony*, *Molped*, *Lady Care* and *Angel Secret* respectively. None of the respondents indicated using or buying the following brand of sanitary pad, *Diva*, *Comfit*, *Kotex*, *Dry Love*, *Stayfree*, *Sofy* and *Queen Lady*.

Table 5: Reasons Why Respondents Buy Particular Brands of Sanitary Pad

	SA	A	UD	D	SD	M
Reasons for buying brands	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	
My brand of sanitary pad is highly hygienic	228 (76%)	36 (12%)	36 (12%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4.64
My brand of sanitary pad is pocket friendly	132 (44%)	48 (16%)	60 (20%)	48 (16%)	12 (4%)	3.8
My brand of sanitary pad is suitable for my heavy flow	192 (64%)	47 (15.7%)	61 (20.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4.44
My brand of sanitary pad comes with plenty pieces in pack	13 (43.7%)	61 (20.3%)	73 (24.3%)	35 (11.7%)	0 (0%)	3.96
I buy cheaper brands of sanitary pad when my preferred brands increase in price	25 (8.3%)	47 (15.7%)	33 (11%)	98 (32.%)	97 (32.3%)	2.35
I don't care about brands of sanitary pads, I just buy whichever one I get in the market	24 (8%)	30 (10%)	30 (10%)	72 (24%)	144 (48%)	2.06

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Key: Strongly Agree-5, Agree-4, Undecided-3, Disagree-2, Strongly disagree-1

Table 5 revealed that a significant majority of the population, 268 (88%) buy a particular brand of sanitary pad because it is highly hygienic. 180 (60%) respondents buy their brand of sanitary pad because it is pocket friendly, 60 (20%) respondents are neutral about the price of sanitary pads while 60 (20%) respondent do not perceive the brand of sanitary pad they use to be pocket friendly.

A preponderant majority of respondents, 239 (79.7%) agree that they buy the brand of sanitary pad they use, because it is suitable for their heavy flow, however 61 (20.3%) respondents are neutral as regards the suitability of their brands of sanitary pad for heavy flow. 192 (64%) respondents buy sanitary pads because it comes with plenty pieces in a pack. 73 (24.7%) respondents are undecided about it while 35 respondents do not buy sanitary pads because of the quantity in the pack. 72 (24%) respondents buy other brands when their preferred brands increase in price, 33 (11%) respondents indicate being neutral on the issue while 195 respondents actively disagree to switching to other brands due to increase in price of preferred brands.

This indicates an average level of brand loyalty among respondents towards preferred brands of sanitary pads. 54 (18%) respondents do not care about brands of sanitary pads, they just buy whichever one they can get in the market, 30 (10%) respondents are undecided on the issue of intentional purchase of brands of sanitary pads while 216 (72%) respondents care about the offerings of the brands of sanitary pads they buy.

In summary, the buying behaviour of Adeleke University female students is influenced by price, quantity, hygiene, and functionality (suitable for heavy flow). It also revealed that Adeleke university female students are highly intentional about the offerings and brands of sanitary pads they purchase and use.

Summary of Findings

This study evaluated sanitary pad advertising messages and the buying behaviour of female students in Adeleke University, Ede using sanitary pads. The researcher sampled 300 respondents using multi stage sampling technique. Research instrument, questionnaire was utilized to collect primary data. The data collected were tabulated and analysed using

the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics analysis was adopted for further data analysis.

The findings of this study revealed that new media and broadcast media are respective prominent channel through which Adeleke University female students' access sanitary pad advertising messages. The specific channel through which Adeleke university female students access sanitary pad advertisement messages are: social media platforms and television respectively. The study revealed that Adeleke University female students to a large extent pay attention to sanitary pad advertisement messages that engage the audience using songs, explore menstrual hygiene education, realistically portray menstrual experiences and are feminist inclined.

Advertising messages to a large extent motivate brand patronage of sanitary pads among female students of Adeleke University. This is hinged on statement of benefits such as no leakage, no skin irritation, and protective wings, among others in sanitary pad advertisement messages. The five popular brands of sanitary pad among female students of Adeleke University are: Always, Virony, Molped, Lady Care and Angel Secret respectively. None of the respondents indicated using or buying the following other seven identified brand of sanitary pad, Diva, Comfit, Kotex, Dry Love, Stayfree, Sofy and Queen Lady.

Also, personal factors such as functionality (suitable for heavy flow), hygiene and large quantity(plenty pieces in a pack) are reasons why Adeleke University female students buy brands of sanitary pads. Affordability and brand loyalty are economic reasons that influence brand patronage of sanitary pads among female students of Adeleke University. Social reasons such as recommendations from friends and families are factors that influence the decision of female students in Adeleke University to buy a particular brand of sanitary pad.

Conclusion

Female students of Adeleke University look out for certain benefits (highly absorbent, hygienic, pocket friendly and skin friendly) in a particular brand of sanitary. One of the means of ascertaining their chosen brand have those qualities before purchase, is through advertisement. The combination of scholarly opinions reviewed and data collected from the field revealed female student of Adeleke University do not access sanitary pad

advertisement messages across all media platforms, just few of them, social media and television .

The three most brands of sanitary pads among respondents are Always, Virony and Molped. These are brands that are strongly advertised. This creates a connection with between advertising messages and brand patronage. Respondents to a very large extent pay attention to sanitary pad advertisement messages to make purchase decisions.

Recommendations

This study was conducted to examine how the attention, interest, desire and action of female students of Adeleke University towards sanitary pad advertisement messages, influence what they buy, who motivates patronage, why they buy, where they buy and how they buy sanitary pads. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Advertisers and Advertising specialists should adopt media diversification as regards placement of sanitary pad advertisement messages. This will enable target markets access sanitary pad advertisement messages from other media platforms not just social media and television.
2. Sanitary pad advertising messages should be creatively tailored towards the information needs of Nigerian women.
3. The study recommends that advertisers and advertising specialists should emphasize the benefits of products in their messages rather than emphasizing entertaining messages to motivate brand patronage of sanitary pads.
4. Manufacturers of Sanitary pad should ensure promise of value made in advertisement is delivered in offerings sold to the public.
5. Advertisers should consider the personal, social and economic reasons that influence consumer buying behaviour in creating sanitary pads and sanitary pad advertisement messages.
6. Advertisers in collaboration with advertising agencies should ensure sanitary pad advertisements reflect realistic menstrual experiences.
7. Advertised brands of sanitary pad are the three most popular brands among respondents; advertisers should invest more in effective advertising as a marketing strategy.

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